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Guidelines for the validation of biomarkers of effect: implementing quality assurance, trueness, precision, and accuracy as well as the availability of quality control measures by qualified laboratories

Intra-laboratory quality control measures for effect biomarkers: fine-tuning, precision (intra- and inter-assay variability) and accuracy

Deliverable Report D14.7

WP14 - Effect biomarkers

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2 Abstract/Summary

Background: Based on the wide literature searches conducted inside WP14, and together with toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) information collected in WP13, both classic and novel effect biomarkers were selected to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies as well as in some existing prospective European birth cohorts. Among the novel biomarkers are the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) protein to be measured in urine, serum and DNA methylation in blood; Kisspeptin protein to be assessed in serum and DNA methylation in blood; the oxidative stress biomarker 8OHdG in urine, and several classic hormonal and metabolic parameters in serum samples. The objective of this deliverable is to present the fine-tuning process and quality controls followed for each effect biomarker; in order to validate the technical measurements performed providing data on assay performance, especially regarding intra- and inter-assay variability.

Methods: Depending on the nature of the effect biomarker (protein, metabolite or molecular marker), different approaches have been followed, mainly for: a) the selection and comparison of different commercial ELISA kits; b) epigenetic measurements following the most up to date quality controls in molecular biology (bisulfite-pyrosequencing for DNA methylation and chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) for histone modifications); and c) high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). The age range of the study population will be considered, especially in the case of hormonal parameters, since the range of measurements should be adapted for each group (children, adolescents or adults). This aspect will affect mainly, but not only, to some of the selected classical biomarkers. Also timing of sampling may be relevant as it is known that many physiological parameters fluctuate during the day.

Results: The technical validity of BDNF protein measurements in urine and serum, as well as DNA methylation in blood has been confirmed. Additionally, serum total BDNF levels and blood DNA methylation was implemented in 134 adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort, and preliminary associations between BPA exposure, BDNF biomarkers and behavioral data support its physiological validity. Urinary BDNF concentrations have been measured in this same population. Kisspeptin-54 protein levels are being assessed in serum samples from both fresh and 1-year-frozen samples subjected to more than 5 freeze-thaw cycles. Kisspeptin DNA methylation in blood has also been validated. Measurement of Kisspeptin-54 protein levels in serum and DNA methylation in blood samples from the INMA-Granada pilot study is currently underway, to evaluate the variability and range of measurements, as well as to assess its physiological validity in relation to reproductive hormones (LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, etc.) before its implementation in the aligned studies. A novel method using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) has been developed and validated for the measurement of urinary 8OHdG concentrations. Finally, the performance and variation in the measurement of classic hormonal (TSH, T3, T4, LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG) and metabolic (TG, TC, HDL-C, LDL-C, Leptin, adiponectin) parameters from a qualified laboratory has been ascertained.

Next Steps: Currently, the assessment of classic parameters, serum BDNF and blood DNA methylation of BDNF, kisspeptin and other molecular targets is being implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies. After confirming the suitability of urinary BDNF and serum Kisspeptin among adolescents from the INMA-Granada pilot study, these biomarkers will be subsequently implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies. After all aligned measurements are finalised, some of the novel effect biomarkers will be implemented in prospective European birth cohorts.

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3 Introduction

Based on the wide literature searches conducted inside WP14, and together with toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) information collected in WP13, both classic and novel effect biomarkers were selected to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies and selected prospective European birth cohorts (D14.2, D14.3 and D14.5).

Among the novel biomarkers are the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) protein to be measured in urine, serum and DNA methylation in blood; Kisspeptin protein to be assessed in serum and DNA methylation in blood; the oxidative stress biomarker 8OHdG in urine, and several classic hormonal and metabolic parameters in serum samples (Table 1).

The objective of this deliverable is to present the fine-tuning process and intra-laboratory quality controls followed for each of the selected HBM4EU effect biomarker; in order to validate the technical measurements performed providing data on assay performance, especially regarding intra- and inter-assay variability. Depending on the nature of the effect biomarker (protein, metabolite or molecular mark), different approaches have been followed, mainly: a) the selection and comparison of different commercial ELISA kits; b) epigenetic measurements following the most up to date quality controls in molecular biology; and c) high-performance liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). In the aligned studies each effect biomarker will be evaluated by the laboratory that performed the quality check, so there was no need to perform an inter-laboratory comparison of effect measurements.

Table 1: Summary of effect biomarkers presented together with the specific laboratory in charge of each measurement

Effect biomarker	Partner	Assay
Serum BDNF protein levels	UGR	ELISA
Urinary BDNF protein levels	UGR	ELISA
Blood DNA methylation	INSERM	Bisulfite-Pyrosequencing
Serum Kisspeptin levels	UGR	ELISA
Histone modification of nuclear receptors	INSERM	Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP)
Urinary 8OHdG levels	MU	HPLC-MS/MS
Serum hormonal and metabolic classic parameters	UGR	Immunosorbent assay

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4 Results

4.1 Serum and urinary BDNF protein concentrations (UGR)

BDNF, is a growth factor from the family of neurotrophins (**Figure 1**), that can play an important role in neurogenesis, neurite growth, synaptic transmission, synaptic plasticity, brain development and learning and memory processes, among others (Bathina and Das, 2015; Lu et al., 2014). BDNF has also been implicated in neuropsychiatric disorders (Autry and Monteggia, 2012). Thus, changes in the expression of BDNF have been reported in several neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer disease, Parkinson and Huntington disease (Zuccato and Cattaneo, 2009).

Furthermore, BDNF has been associated with the exposure to some chemical pollutants such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) or perfluorooctanoic acids (PFOS) (Li et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2015).

Within WP14, BDNF has been selected as a novel effect biomarker of neurodevelopment in the HBM4EU project. Previous studies have shown that BDNF can be assessed in serum and urine samples using immunosorbent assays. Therefore, UGR (14.3 HBM4EU partner), WP14 leader, has fine-tuned a methodology to measure this neurotrophic factor in both serum and urine samples, before implementing these biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Figure 1: Secretion and intra-extracellular maturation procedures of BDNF (Kowiański et al., 2018)

Several experimental conditions have been performed in order to obtain the most appropriate methodology according to its recovery, range values and intra- and inter-assay variations, among others quality parameters. With this purpose, and based on previous studies, UGR has made some trials with different treatments of biological sample preparation, measurement and storage conditions, sample volumes, and commercial based enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits. As a result, UGR has fine-tuned and technically validated the methodology to quantify this neurotrophic factor in both urine and serum samples.

Moreover, serum BDNF assessment has already been implemented in the INMA-Granada birth cohort as a pilot study, and urinary BDNF is being measured in the same cohort, in order to complete the QA/QC protocol. The aim of this pilot study is to assess its technical validity before BDNF implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

HUMAN SERUM SAMPLES

Firstly, UGR validated the appropriate methodology to measure this neurotrophic factor in human serum samples.

Quality Control (QC)

According to the designed quality control, each serum sample has been tested in duplicates by using two different plates. Initially, a volume of 20 µL of serum is picked up and diluted 1:100, as it is shown in the figure below (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Procedure followed for samples dilutions

After sample dilution, the calibration curve is performed. Thus, standards are made to get the following concentrations (**Figure 3**).

C (10000pg/ml)= Std reconstituted with distilled water

S1 (1000pg/ml)= 50µl Std+450µl RD5K

S2 (500pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S1

S3 (250pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S2

S4 (125pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S3

S5 (62,5pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S4

S6 (31,3pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S5

S7 (15,6pg/ml)= 200µl Std + 200µl S6

Figure 3: Standards used for calibration curve

Finally, standards and samples are added into wells according to the quality control design, briefly explained as follows; Rows 1 and 2 are designed for standards, while rows 3 to 12 are designed to add samples. Concretely, diluted samples will be charged in rows 3 to 11 from plate 1 and their duplicates will be charged in plate 2, so that the inter-assay coefficient of variability (CV) can be calculated. To obtain the intra-assay CV, duplicates of row 11 will be charged in row 12. To guarantee the lowest possible variability in the measurements, the analysis of BDNF (serum, urine and methylations) are carried out by a single operator; although other aspects such as season and temperature, were also be taken into account.

Figure 4: Quality control designed in order to measure BDNF in serum samples (AD.14.6)

Total serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) was measured with an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using a Quantikine® ELISA kit (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA). Serum samples from boys (n=134) belonging to the Spanish INMA-Granada birth cohort. During the last follow up visit (2017-2019) of the INMA-Granada, 155 males adolescents at the age 15–17 years agreed to participate and underwent both physical and psychological examination at the San Cecilio University Hospital (Granada, Spain). Whole venous blood was collected from participants (n=134) at 5-7 PM, processed, and stored at -80°C until analysis (Castiello et al., 2020). Serum samples were defrosted, vortexed, aliquoted in 10 µL, diluted 1:100 times and tested according to manufacturer's instructions at the Centre of Biomedical Research (CIBM) from the University of Granada (Spain).

Serum BDNF levels ranged from 14.25 ng/mL to 65.75 ng/ml, and mean and geometric mean were 34.8 and 33.7 ng/mL, respectively. Distribution of total serum BDNF concentrations were as follows: P25th = 29.1 ng/mL, P50th= 34.6 ng/mL and P75th= 39.7 ng/mL (**Figure 5**).

Routine calibration curves were conducted to acknowledge the quality of serum BDNF measurement. As four plates were required, based on the quality control design (AD14.6), four calibration curves were conducted (see figures above). R² was 0.999 in all cases.

Assembly of the BDNF microplate

Microplate #1

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	C+	C+	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	57	65	65
B	S1	S1	2	10	18	26	34	42	50	58	66	66
C	S2	S2	3	11	19	27	35	43	51	59	67	67
D	S3	S3	4	12	20	28	36	44	52	60	68	68
E	S4	S4	5	13	21	29	37	45	53	61	69	69
F	S5	S5	6	14	22	30	38	46	54	62	70	70
G	S6	S6	7	15	23	31	39	47	55	63	71	71
H	S7	S7	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	72	72

Microplate #2

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	C+	C+	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	57	65	65
B	S1	S1	2	10	18	26	34	42	50	58	66	66
C	S2	S2	3	11	19	27	35	43	51	59	67	67
D	S3	S3	4	12	20	28	36	44	52	60	68	68
E	S4	S4	5	13	21	29	37	45	53	61	69	69
F	S5	S5	6	14	22	30	38	46	54	62	70	70
G	S6	S6	7	15	23	31	39	47	55	63	71	71
H	S7	S7	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	72	72

Figure 5: Assembly of plates and distribution of serum BDNF concentration (ng/mL) within adolescent from the INMA-Granada cohort, (n=134). On the left, it is shown the dispersion of the concentrations of serum BDNF. On the right, the range of BDNF concentrations in serum among the participants is shown in a histogram

Comparison with serum BDNF levels from previous epidemiologic studies

In order to assess the comparability of the obtained serum BDNF concentrations, UGR conducted a brief search of the scientific data, based on PubMed. The objective of this brief search (showed in **table 2**) was to look for levels of serum BDNF previously published and compare them with the levels obtained from the INMA-Granada cohort.

Briefly, inclusion criteria were: i) scientific articles published in the last 10 years; ii) epidemiological studies; iii) BDNF should have been measured in serum samples with immunosorbent assays and iv) only measures of BDNF concentrations from healthy people will be included. If the study was a randomised control trial, only data from controls was included. Search terms included (brain-derived neurotrophic factor OR BDNF) AND (serum AND adolescents).

Table 2: Serum BDNF levels found in the scientific literature from epidemiological studies

Study			BDNF Concentration		Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Mean				
(J.M., 2016)	Case-control study	Controls n=9 adolescents16. 3 years old	20.9 ng/mL		BDNF	Serum	R&D system (Minneapolis, MN, USA) kit using a Sino Biological kit (Sino Biological Inc., Beijing, China)
(Naegelin et al., 2018)	Methodological study	259 healthy participants; 44.31 years old	Female 32.9 ng/mL Males 32.3 ng/mL		BDNF	Serum	Combination of BDNF monoclonal antibodies designated mAb BDNF-#1 and mAb BDNF-#9 (Kolbeck et al., 1999).

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Study		BDNF Concentration		Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Mean			
(Pedersen et al., 2017)	Cross-sectional study	447 healthy adolescents 11-17 years old	Female 26.9 ng/mL Male 27 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Quantikine, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA
(Piccinni et al., 2008)	Descriptive Study	28 adults (Men=28-32 years old; Women=25-32 years old)	Plasma: Male 7.82 ng/ml Female 5.48 ng/ml Serum: Male 38.1 ng/ml Female 37 ng/ml	Total BDNF	Plasma and serum	Promega, Wallisellen, Switzerland
(Huang et al., 2017)	Cross-sectional study	Boys and girls (n=415), 14 years old	Boys= 27.3ng/mL Girls= 26.8 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Quantikine® ELISA, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA
(Oddone et al., 2017)	Case-control study	Controls= 15 (62.2 years)	Values 313.6 pg/ml	Total BDNF	Serum	ELISA (code DY248; sensitivity 20pg/ml; R&D System)
(Cho et al., 2017)	Case-control prepuberal 11-12 yrs old	Cases=30 ; Controls= 15 (both at 9-12 years)	Case 24.45 ng/ml Control 24.00 ng/ml	Total BDNF	Serum	Quantikine Kit (Catalog No. DBD00; R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA)
(Zhao et al., 2017)	Case-control study	44 healthy controls, 29.2 years old	m-BDNF= 353.8 pg/mL; p-BDNF= 92.13 pg/mL; Ratio m/po= 4.6	m-BDNF; p-BDNF; Ratio m/p	Plasma	ELISA kits(Shanghai Bogoo Biotechnology Co., Ltd. Shanghai, China) (Code number: HEB005 and HEP142 for mBDNF an f proBDNF respectively)
(Fonseca-Portilla et al., 2019)	Case-control Study	active women= 195; 40 yrs old; non active women= 154 40 yrs old	active: 33 ng/mL; non active 34 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Applied Biosystems, CA

Study		BDNF Concentration		Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Mean			
(Ormstad et al., 2018)	Case-control study	n= 30 children; 10.9 years	BDNF 21.2 ng/mL; pro-BDNF= 4.9 ng/mL	BDNF and PRO-BDNF	Serum	Plasma levels of BDNF and PRO-BDNF were assessed using Derived Neurotrophic Factor ELISA kit and Human Pro Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor ELISA kit obtained Nordic BioSite, Sweden.
(Mora et al., 2019)	Case-control study	n= 49 healthy controls; 48.3 years old	40.0 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	sandwich-ELISA, using a commercial kit according to the manufacturer's instructions (Chemicon, Temecula, CA, USA),
(Yurteri et al., 2019)	Case-control study	24 boys with 10.5 years old	BDNF 14.87 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay: Fine Biological Technology Co. Ltd, cat. No: EH-0043
(Aksu et al., 2018)	Case-control study	30 adolescent 14.7 years old	1.04 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Human BDNF ELISA Kit (Boster Immunoleader, USA),
(Alomari et al., 2018)	Cross-sectional study	288 healthy adolescents 14 years old	Boys 11 µg/dL Girls 15 µg/dL	BDNF	Serum	Human BDNF Duoset Kit R&D system, USA
(Jeon and Ha, 2017)	Randomised control trial	49 healthy male 15 years old	27.04 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	ELISA (sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbant assay) Kit (Promega, USA)

HUMAN URINE SAMPLES

UGR objective was also to develop a validated methodology for human urine samples. Thus, UGR has fine-tuned the methodology to quantify this neurotrophic factor in this biological matrix. Several experimental designs have been tested:

- Pre-treatment of urine samples: acidification plus extraction, lyophilisation and centrifugation steps.
- Several conditions: with/without pre-treatment, with/without dilutions.

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- Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay: 7 commercial brands have been tested: **R&D System** (Quantikine® Total BDNF), **Elabscience** (Human BDNF ELISA Kit- E-EL-H0010), **Abcam** (Human BDNF Elisa kit - ab212166), **Phoenix Pharmaceuticals** (Human BDNF Elisa kit - EK-033-22), **Abcam** (Human BDNF Elisa kit - ab999789), **Biobyrt** (Human BDNF Elisa kit - orb50004) and **RayBiotech** (Human BDNF Elisa - ELH-BDNF).

After those experimental approaches, we have selected the best measurement conditions and the methodological assay should develop as follow:

- A pre-treatment of the samples: urine samples should be treated following the protocol published by Collins and Koven (Collins and Koven, 2014; Koven and Collins, 2014) with minor modifications (3 ml of the acetonitrile 80%, as extraction step).
- A minimum urinary volume of 600 µL.
- Use of the ELISA kit supplied by Raybiotech (Human BDNF Elisa - ELH-BDNF), which showed the best performance.

Quality Control (QC)

According to the quality control, all standards of calibration curve, zero standard and each urine samples is tested in duplicate within the ELISA microplate. The typical quality control is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Quality control designed for urinary BDNF measurements

The ELISA kit assay, supplied by RayBiotech, has similar features as the Abcam kit (ab999789), initially tested but withdrawn during the QA/QC process from the market. The ELISA kit supplied by RayBiotech includes two diluents for serum/plasma samples and for cell culture medium. The latter has been chosen for BDNF measurements in urine samples because the resulting BDNF levels are in the range of those published in the scientific literature (Collins and Koven, 2014; K. et al., 2016; Koven and Collins, 2014) and this kit showed the best performance.

We developed a protocol for the preparation of urine samples that included the acidification and extraction of the biological samples before testing them in the assay following the manufacturer's

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recommendations. Urinary samples (600 μL) are treated following the protocol established by Collins & Koven (Collins and Koven, 2014; Koven and Collins, 2014) with minor modifications (**Figure 7**). Thus, in the **acidification step**, 600 μL of samples are first treated with 300 μL of 1.5% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and then centrifuged for 15 minutes at 4000 rpm at 4°C. In the **extraction step**, the supernatant is loaded into Strata-XL 60 mg cartridge, previously equilibrated with 1 ml methanol (MeOH) and 1 mL distilled water, and allowed to drain. The columns are then washed with 0.1% TFA (1 mL), followed by vacuum suction for 10 minutes to rid any residual fluids. The cartridge is then eluted with 3 mL of acetonitrile (80%), and the resulting eluent evaporated to total dryness under a stream of nitrogen.

The resulting dried extract samples are assessed in the ELISA kit following the indications of the commercial brand.

Figure 7: Acidification and extraction steps for the assessment of BDNF levels in urine samples.

Assembly of the BDNF microplate

Reagents for standard curves

- **Assay Diluent B** should be diluted 5-fold with distilled water before use (15 ml diluent B and 60 ml Milli-Q water).
- **Wash Buffer:** Dilute 20 ml of Wash Buffer Concentrate into distilled water to yield 400 mL of 1X Wash Buffer (20 mL Wash buffer 20X and 380 mL Milli-Q water)
- **Detection Antibody Concentrate vial:** Add 100 μL of 1X Assay Diluent B into each vial to prepare this reactive.
 - **Detection Antibody:** The detection antibody concentrate should be diluted 80-fold with 1X Assay Diluent B (200 μL detection antibody concentrate and 16 ml 1X Assay Diluent B).
- **HRP-Streptavidin** concentrate should be diluted 200-fold with 1X Assay Diluent B (75 μL HRP-Streptavidin concentrate and 15 mL 1X Assay Diluent B).

Figure 8: Standard curve preparation

The standard curve is prepared with seven points of calibration (**Figure 8**).

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Stock Solution (400 ng/ml) = powder + 720 ul Diluent B

Std. 1 (16 ng/ml) = 40 μ L Stock + 960 μ L Diluent B

Std. 2 (6.4 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 1 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Std. 3 (2.56 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 2 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Std. 4 (1.02 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 3 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Std. 5 (0.41 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 4 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Std. 6 (0.16 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 5 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Std. 7 (0.06 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Std. 6 + 300 μ L Diluent B

Zero Std. (0 ng/ml) = 300 μ L Diluent B

Urine Samples

Dried extracts of each urine sample is reconstituted with 200 μ L of 1X Assay Diluent B, in order to assess each sample in duplicate, as indicated in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Diagram of the protocol to determine BDNF in urine samples

ELISA kit procedure

- Add 100 μ L of each standard and samples into appropriated wells. Cover well and incubate for 2.5 hours at room temperature with gentle shaking.
- Discard the solution and wash four times with 1X wash solution (300 μ L/well). Complete removal of liquid at each step is essential for a good performance. After the last wash, remove any remaining 1X wash Buffer by aspirating or decanting. Invert the plate and blot it against clean paper towels.
- Add 100 μ L of 1X biotinylated antibody to each well. Incubate for one hour at room temperature with gentle shaking.
- Discard the solution. Repeat the washes with 300 μ L 1X wash buffer.

- Add 100 µL of 1X Streptavidin solution to each well. Incubate for forty-five minutes at room temperature with gentle shaking.
- Discard the solution. Repeat the washes with 300 µL 1X wash buffer.
- Add 100 µL of TMB One-Step Substrate Reagent to each well. Incubate for thirty minutes at room temperature in the dark with gentle shaking.
- Add 50 µL of Stop Solution to each well. Read the plate at 450 nm immediately

Standard Curve

An example of a typical BDNF standard curve is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Human BDNF standard curve

Assembly of the BDNF microplate

Urine samples were assembled in the BDNF microplate as in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Assembly of BDNF microplate

Results

Table 3 shows the final concentration of BDNF (ng/ml) in human urine samples tested in the ELISA kit supplied by RayBiotech (and **Table 4** summarised the main statistic parameters associated with the BDNF data). Figure 12 shows the histogram with the 15 selected urine samples. **Table 5** summarised the mean BDNF concentrations found in previous epidemiological studies. All urinary BDNF concentrations obtained were within the range of levels published in some of the studies found in the literature review (Antunes-Lopes et al., 2017; Collins and Koven, 2014; K. et al., 2016; Koven and Collins, 2014).

Figure 12: Range of BDNF concentrations in the selected urine samples

Table 3: Absorbance (at 450 nm) and final concentration (ng/mL) of frozen urine samples (n=15) tested in the ELISA kit supplied by RayBiotech

Samples (600 µL)	Absorbance			Concentration		
	OD 450 nm		Mean ± SD	ng/ml		Mean ± SD
M1	0.501	0.484	0.493 ± 0.012	2.902	2.816	2.859 ± 0,061
M2	0.354	0.333	0.344 ± 0.015	2.129	2.013	2.071 ± 0,082
M3	0.510	0.320	0.415 ± 0.134	2.947	1.941	2.444 ± 0,712
M4	0.355	0.731	0.543 ± 0.266	2.135	4.000	3.067 ± 1,319
M5	0.330	0.313	0.322 ± 0.012	1.997	1.901	1.949 ± 0,067
M6	0.441	0.548	0.495 ± 0.076	2.594	3.136	2.865 ± 0,383
M7	0.504	0.498	0.501 ± 0.004	2.917	2.887	2.902 ± 0,021
M8	0.143	0.230	0.187 ± 0.062	0.883	1.420	1.152 ± 0,380
M9	0.563	0.569	0.566 ± 0.004	3.210	3.239	3.225 ± 0,021
M10	0.279	0.288	0.284 ± 0.006	1.708	1.759	1.734 ± 0,037
M11	0.716	0.694	0.705 ± 0.016	3.931	3.831	3.881 ± 0,071
M12	0.067	0.094	0.081 ± 0.019	0.381	0.563	0.472 ± 0,129
M13	0.157	0.096	0.127 ± 0.043	0.972	0.577	0.774 ± 0,280
M14	0.517	0.463	0.490 ± 0.038	2.983	2.708	2.845 ± 0,194
M15	0.315	0.285	0.300 ± 0.021	1.913	1.742	1.827 ± 0,121

Table 4: Statistics parameters for the 15 human urine samples tested

Statistic Parameters	
Mean	2.271
Median	2.444
Standard deviation	0.962
Min.	0.472
Max.	3.881
Intra-Assay CV	11.4%

Urinary BDNF was also measured in the same adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada birth cohort from whom also serum BDNF levels were assessed, as a pilot study, in order to complete the QA/QC protocol and assess its relationship with serum BDNF levels, blood DNA methylation and behavior data. The aim of this pilot study was to assess its physiological validity before implementing urinary BDNF measurements in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Distribution of urinary BDNF concentrations in 134 adolescents from the INMA-Granada

Figure 13: Distribution of urinary BDNF levels in INMA-Granada

Intra-Assay CV (%) = 3.67
Inter-Assay CV (%) = 14.61

Urinary BDNF levels ranged from <LOD ng/mL to 7.40 ng/ml. Distribution of urinary BDNF concentrations were as follows: P25th = 2.88 ng/mL, P50th= 4.23 ng/mL and P75th= 5.37 ng/mL

Comparison with urinary BDNF levels from previous epidemiologic studies

In order to assess the comparability of the obtained urinary BDNF concentrations, UGR conducted a brief search of the scientific data in the PubMed database. The objective of this brief search was to look for levels of urinary BDNF previously published.

Briefly, inclusion criteria were: i) scientific articles published in the last 10 years; ii) epidemiological studies; iii) BDNF had been measured in urinary samples with immunosorbent assays and iv) Measurements of BDNF concentrations from healthy and unhealthy populations were included. Selected search terms were: (brain-derived neurotrophic factor OR BDNF) AND (urinary AND children/adolescents/adults). **Table 5** summarises urinary BDNF levels found in the scientific literature from epidemiological studies.

Table 5: Urinary BDNF levels found in the scientific literature (healthy and unhealthy populations)

Article	ELISA kit	Urine BDNF levels
(Pinto et al., 2010)	Emax® ImmunoAssay System (Promega, USA)	Not included
(Antunes-Lopes et al., 2013)	Emax® ImmunoAssay System (Promega, USA)	110.4 ± 159.5 pg/mg Cr
(Wang et al., 2014)	ELISA kit (BioTeck Instruments, Inc., Winooski, VT, USA)	1.25-2.04 pg/ mg Cr

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Article	ELISA kit	Urine BDNF levels
(Collins and Koven, 2014)	ab99978 BDNF Human ELISA Kit from Abcam (Cambridge, Mass., USA)	0.1-7.9 ng/ml
(Koven and Collins, 2014)	ab99978 BDNF Human ELISA Kit from Abcam (Cambridge, Mass., USA)	0.1-7.9 ng/ml
(Jiang et al., 2014)	Emax® ImmunoAssay System (Promega, USA)	9.57 ± 5.37 pg/ml
(Alkis et al., 2017)	ELISA kit (Brand not included)	340.2 ± 199 ng/mg Cr
(Pennycuff et al., 2017)	Phoenix Pharmaceuticals Inc. (Burlingame, CA)	4.7 ± 5.4 pg/ml
(Ozdemir. et al., 2016)	ab99978 BDNF Human ELISA Kit from Abcam (Cambridge, Mass., USA)	0.81 ± 0.7 ng/mg Cr
(Antunes-Lopes et al., 2017)	Emax® ImmunoAssay System (Promega, USA)	2.47 ± 0.44 pg/mg Cr
(Wang et al., 2017)	ELISA kit (Boster, China)	1.71 ± 0.55 pg/ml
(Chen et al., 2017)	ELISA kit (BioVision, CA, USA)	77.4 ± 47.7 pg/ml
(Russo et al., 2018)	ELISA kit (Biorbyt, Explore Bioreagent, UK)	32-53 pg/mg Cr
(Peyronnet et al., 2019)	BDNF ELISA KIT (Raybiotech)	5.23 ± 4.8 pg/mg Cr
(Ece et al., 2019)	ELISA kit (Sun Red Biological Technology Co. Ltd, Shangai, China)	0.008-0.019 pg/mg Cr
(Morizawa et al., 2019)	Emax® ImmunoAssay System (Promega, USA)	0.0094-14.80 BDNF/Cr ratio
(Rada et al., 2020)	ELISA kit (Elabscience, Houston, TX)	Not included

Urinary determination of Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF) by Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

Several different commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays have been tested in order to develop a validated methodology for human urine samples.

After reviewing the scientific literature, it was observed that the kit most used in studies that determine BDNF in urine was supplied by **Promega (Emax® ImmunoAssay System)** (Pinto et al., 2010; Antunes-Lopes et al., 2013; Jiang et al., 2014; Antunes-Lopes et al., 2016; Morizawa et al., 2019). Unfortunately, this product was discontinued, for the reason it could not be used in the validation of the methodology for the quantification of BDNF in urine samples.

Several other commercial Elisa kits were found in several studies to determine BDNF in urine (Polacchini et al., 2014; Rada et al., 2020; Pennycuff et al., 2016; Russo et al., 2017). For this reason, the ELISA kit supplied by **R&D System (Quantikine® Total BDNF)**, **Elabscience (Human BDNF ELISA Kit E-EL-H0010)** and **Phoenix Pharmaceuticals (EK-033-22)** were acquired and tested in human urine samples, following the methodology previously described (i.e., with or without pre-treatment) (Polacchini et al., 2014; Rada et al., 2020; Pennycuff et al., 2016). All the samples tested with these three brands were below the limit of detection (LOD). Moreover, the ELISA kit supplied by **Biobryt (BDNF Human ELISA - orb50004)** was used (Russo et al., 2017). We tested this last assay, with or without sample pre-treatment. The results obtained showed a very low reproducibility in the duplicated samples assessed.

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Additionally, the **Human ELISA BDNF (catalog #ab212166)** supplied by **Abcam** was also tested. The samples were, again, assessed with or without pre-treatment (lyophilised) and with and without sample dilutions. Data obtained showed that the diluent used to dilute the samples interfered with the optical density of the sample, as well as with the final BDNF concentration. The pre-treatment of lyophilisation of the samples also could interfere in the BDNF concentration (checked with a fortified urine sample with BDNF stock solution).

Consequently, all the aforementioned kits were not adequate to determine BDNF concentrations in human urine samples.

BDNF assessment was continued with a new other **ELISA kit supplied by Abcam (catalog #ab999789)** (Koven & Collins, 2014; Collins & Koven, 2014; Ozdemir et al., 2016). This kit was used to test urine samples with and without pre-treatment. After carrying out several assays with this kit, it was possible to optimise the protocol selecting the best diluent (Diluent B), the best pre-treated step [the one described by Collins and Koven's protocol (Koven & Collins, 2014 and Collins & Koven, 2014), with minor modifications], and the more appropriated volume of urine for this methodology. Unfortunately, after the protocol was fine-tuned, this **ELISA kit supplied by Abcam** was discontinued by the company.

However, an exhaustive search in different companies was carried out to find a kit with similar features (reagents, standard curve and protocol) as the one previously standardised (**Abcam, catalog #ab999789**). A new kit supplied by **Raybiotech (Human ELISA kit – ELH-BDNF)** (Peyronnet et al., 2019) was then tested. This one has been selected as the optimal kit for the assessment of BDNF in human urine samples following the protocol described above.

4.2 BDNF DNA methylation (INSERM)

Quality control methods employed for the analyses of BDNF DNA Methylation. Importantly, this quality control will be applied exactly the same way for the evaluation of DNA methylation in the case of Kisspeptin and the Thyroid Receptor (TR).

a) Quality Control of DNA using QuantiFluor and NanoDrop

The first step involved in DNA methylation is the quality control of DNA. If an already extracted DNA is provided for the analyses, DNA concentration is re-measured using QuantiFluor double-stranded (dsDNA) system (Promega, France). This method uses a dye that is specific for dsDNA so that the exact amount of dsDNA could be measured, which is important for all downstream analyses. If blood samples are provided, DNA is extracted using silica-based columns available from DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen, France). This method provides high quality DNA that is completely free of RNA due to RNase treatment during extraction. The extracted DNA is always stored at -80°C until use. DNA concentration is also measured by using NanoDrop to observe the A260/280 ratio. The A260/280 ratio or the absorbance values at 260 nm vs 280 nm is an indicator of nucleic acid purity. The A260/280 value for pure dsDNA in a buffer solution is between 1.8-1.9, and an increase or decrease in the ratio indicates contamination by proteins or solvents. Given below (**Figure 14**) is an example of the A260/280 ratio (highlighted with red box; 260/280) measured for the extracted INMA adolescent DNA samples that were provided by UGR. All the samples had an A260/280 ratio between 1.8 and 1.9 indicating that the DNA is pure. The genomic DNA was also ran on a 0.7% agarose gel to ensure DNA integrity and absence of any fragmentation/ degradation.

Figure 14: A260/280 ratio (highlighted with red box; 260/280) measured for the extracted INMA adolescent DNA samples

b) Bisulfite Conversion of DNA and quality control using NanoDrop

The next step is bisulfite conversion of DNA, and it is achieved by using EpiTect Fast Bisulfite Conversion kit (Qiagen, France) as per the manufacturer's instructions. For bisulfite conversion, 500 ng of DNA is usually used. During bisulfite conversion, the intact dsDNA gets transformed to single-stranded fragments, wherein, all unmethylated cytosines get converted to uracil. Since bisulfite conversion typically involves treatment of DNA with harsh chemicals such as sodium bisulfite, an ample loss of DNA is expected. However, by using Qiagen kit, as promised by the manufacturer, we could always recover 80% of the bisulfite-converted DNA. Some of the samples are bisulfite converted in duplicates to ensure the efficiency of bisulfite conversion. Following bisulfite conversion, the concentration of DNA is measured by using NanoDrop by using 'RNA-40' as the sample type because bisulfite-converted DNA behaves more like RNA due to presence of single-strand fragments and due to incorporation of uracil. No variation in concentration among the samples suggests absence of technical error in the experiment, absence of contamination from histones and RNA. The bisulfite-converted DNA are highly unstable, and hence, are stored at -80°C and used for further analyses shortly.

c) Amplification of the target gene (BDNF): Quality control on agarose gel

Following bisulfite conversion, bisulfite-converted DNA (BS- converted DNA) is amplified by using the bisulfite-specific primers for the target genes (in this case, BDNF). Amplification of the target gene is achieved by using EpiTaq HS for BS- converted DNA (Takara R110A, Takara Bio Inc, Japan). EpiTaq HS is a hot-start (HS) DNA polymerase enzyme that is optimised for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) involving bisulfite-converted DNA. The primers used (showed in **Table 6**) are also specific for BS-converted DNA and normally range between 26-35 bases with an amplicon size of 150-300 base pairs.

For BDNF methylation, we analysed promoter IV which contains the CREB-binding site (cAMP response element-binding site) and six CpGs (CpG 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 & 6). The genomic co-ordinates of the amplified region are as follows: chr11:27,723,070–27,723,280, and were retrieved from UCSC Genome Browser Human February 2009 (GRCh37/hg19) Assembly (Kundakovic et al., 2015). The reverse primer was biotinylated and the expected product size is 210 base pairs. The PCR conditions were optimised according to manufacturer's instructions (Takara Bio Inc, Japan).

Table 6: Primers used to measure BDNF

Gene	Forward primer	Reverse primer
BDNF	GATTTTGGTAATTAGTGTAT TAGAGTGTT	/5Biosg/ATCAACCAAAAACCTCCATT TAATCTC

Following bisulfite conversion, the PCR products are purified on silica-based column using MinElute PCR Purification kit (Qiagen, France) and the DNA concentration is measured by QuantiFlour double-stranded (dsDNA) system (Promega, France). The amplified BDNF products for all the samples were loaded on a 2% agarose gel and a single product (210 base pair) was observed which indicates the BDNF primer specificity and absence of primer-dimers. The following image (**Figure 15**) is given as an example to show 96 INMA samples loaded on a 2% agarose gel. A homogenous, single BDNF product can be observed for all the samples indicating successful bisulfite conversion of the product and PCR amplification of a single BDNF product at the desired amplicon size, ie. 210 base pair size. Absence of primer-dimer must be ensured; if primer-dimers are visible in the gel, the quantity of primers must be reduced during PCR reaction or other PCR conditions must be optimised (for example, increasing the melt temperature, increasing the number of cycles etc.). For INMA blood, the following image shows the absence of primer-dimers and presence of a single BDNF product.

Figure 15: Bisulfite conversio and PCR amplification of BDNF product

d) Pyrosequencing quality control

Pyrosequencing is a PCR based method that works on sequence-by-synthesis principle. During pyrosequencing, the biotinylated PCR product is strand separated to create a single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) template, to which, the pyrosequencing primer anneals to extend the complementary strand by addition of nucleotides sequentially. The pyrosequencing instrument (Pyromark Q24) can monitor the incorporation of nucleotides through enzymatic conversion of released pyrophosphate into a proportional light signal.

The Pyromark Q24 instrument has certain features that could quality control the complete bisulfite DNA conversion. When the assay encounters a cytosine nucleotide without a subsequent guanine (ie. an unmethylated cytosine in a non-CpG region), the cytosine is expected to be converted to thymine if the bisulfite treatment was successful, and the pyrogram presents it as T=100%. This serves as a good quality control for the conversion of unmethylated cytosine residues during bisulfite treatment and PCR.

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The pyrosequencing assay will be also performed with amplicons generated from DNA with known methylation levels. Commercially available control human DNA that is methylated and unmethylated (Qiagen, France) is used to prepare known methylated standard curve (0%, 10%, 50% and 100% methylated DNA). Pyrosequencing will be performed on known methylated DNA standards to see if linearity can be obtained and there is no bias in PCR. Also, water is used as a negative control for pyrosequencing. The following image is shown as an example of a pyrogram of a sample from INMA adolescent sample (left) and water is shown as a negative control (on the right). The INMA sample passed the quality control of PyroMark Q24 machine and the pyrogram indicates the levels of methylation corresponding to each CpGs, and in the water samples, no levels of methylation could be detected. Any sample that does not pass the quality check are always redone and re-sequenced.

4.3 Histone modification measurements (INSERM)

In the aligned studies, histone modification markers will be studied for several nuclear receptors including ER, AR, GR, PPAR α and PPAR γ . Before their implementation in the aligned studies, INSERM assessed these targets in samples from the INMA-Granada cohort to ensure the quality of these measurement. Below we present some of these results.

Histone H3K4me3 occupancy was assessed at the promoters of genes from 200 μ l blood from the INMA-Granada cohort because this mark is associated with active gene transcription. Briefly, using chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP), the H3K4me3 associated DNA was isolated from blood, quantity was measured and equal amount of starting or immunoprecipitated DNA was taken for qPCR. For the analysis, we chose the primers in promoters of genes, which are associated with nuclear receptors, DNA damage and detoxification activities related functions.

The data was analysed with the help of Bio-Rad CFX Manager software. A good melt curve with a single amplicon could be observed for all the PCR products indicating the specificity of the primers and the absence of primer-dimers. We used as control, the region of GAPDH gene that is located far from the transcription start site, in general, the amplified PCR in this region represent the background and could be used for normalisation. The normalised target copy number data with GAPDH as the reference gene was obtained for all the samples. The basic measurement of ChIP experiment functioning is “immunoprecipitation efficiency” or “ChIP: input ratio” for a given genomic region, which is defined as the amount of PCR product in the ChIP sample divided by the amount of PCR product in the input sample. There was high enrichment for most of the analysed genes, indicating the efficiency of ChIP experiment.

Classification of samples into three groups based on analyses of H3K4me3 mark at *H2AFX* promoter (a marker of DNA damage): We first analysed the *H2AFX* gene and plotted the normalised values in a cluster dendrogram. Three distinct groups of samples could be observed based on the H3K4me3 occupancy at the *H2AFX* gene.

Figure 16: The cluster dendrogram (right) showing H3K4me3 occupancy at H2AFX in INMA-Granada samples. Three groups could be observed with 41 samples in low-H2AFX group, 64 samples in medium-group and 14 samples in high H2AFX group (Kruskal-Wallis's test, chi-squared = 94.632, df = 2, $p < 2.2 \cdot e^{-16}$ Pairwise Mann-Whitney)

For the analyses of the histone occupancy at the promoters of all the other genes tested in this study (**Figure 17**), we maintained the three groups that was observed based on H3K4me3 occupancy for H2AFX.

Figure 17: The graph represents the average values of copy numbers from Group 1 (blue) and Group 2 (green) and Group 3 (Red) for each gene normalised against GAPDH

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Notably, for **BDNF** and **KISS1** genes, primers could not be designed due to absence of H3K4me3 peaks in blood cells, suggesting the absence or very low expression of these factors in nucleated cells of the blood, in contrast to placenta where these factors are present. The genomic view of H3K4me3 peaks for placenta (blue) and blood (red) and for BDNF (left) and KISS1 (right) is given in **Figure 18**. Note the very low peaks or absence of peaks for H3K4me3 in blood samples (red) while the presence of peaks in placenta (blue) for both genes.

Figure 18: Genomic view of H3K4me3 peaks for placenta (blue) and blood (red) and for BDNF (left) and KISS1 (right)

Therefore, both these genes can be analysed only by DNA methylation.

Our results suggest that based on the levels of γ H2AX, which is well known marker of DNA damage (Mah et al., 2010), some samples have high level of DNA damage, and these samples generally have high levels of H3K4me3 occupancy which could be due to higher transcriptional activity. It has been shown that women who smoked during pregnancy have hyperactive epigenetic state in several genes in their children persists into adolescence (Bauer et al., 2016).

4.4 Serum Kisspeptin protein concentrations (UGR)

Within Human Biomonitoring for Europe (HBM4EU) project, Kisspeptin has been recently proposed as novel effect biomarker to assess the adverse effect of chemical pollutants on reproductive outcomes and to be used as a mediator of this exposure-effect association at an epidemiological level.

In this report, it is shown the first trial which aim was to detect KISS 54 in serum samples with different times of conservation. Concretely, 10 serum samples taken from the hospital and immediately tested in less than 24 hours and 10 serum samples kept at -20 °C for more than one year.

KISS 54 was detected in both serum groups (fresh samples with less than 24 hours and frozen samples kept at -20 °C more than one year). Limit of detection (LOD) was 0.08 pg/mL; mean (SD) concentration of KISS 54 in 24 h-serum group was 1.6 (0.1) ng/mL and in one-year-serum group was 1.8 (0.1) ng/mL. No statistical differences were found between groups, however, little bit more concentration of KISS 54 was found in one-year-serum group.

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4.4.1 Background: What is Kisspeptin?

Kisspeptin, also called *metastin* for its role in metastasis suppression, makes reference to a family of peptide hormones of diverse amino acid length, which are cleaved from the product of KISS1 gene in primates (Zhu et al., 2016). Kisspeptin peptides share a common carboxy-terminal sequence through which they are bound to their receptor, encoded as KISS1R/Kiss1r. Concretely, KISS54 refers to the number of amino acids in the peptide once it is cleaved (Popa et al., 2008).

This neuropeptide is secreted by kisspeptin neurons in the hypothalamus, and stimulates the production of gonadotrophin-releasing hormone (GnRH), through its binding to KISS1R upon GnRH neurons, into the local hypophyseal-portal circulation (Orlando et al., 2018).

In 2003, two studies identified its critical role in reproduction, thus demonstrating that absence of KISS1R resulted in failure of puberty and subsequently, infertility (Zhu et al., 2016). Afterwards, a wide range of studies have studied the role of kisspeptin in reproduction and have placed it signalling at the apex of the hypothalamus-pituitary-gonadal axis (HPG). When GnRH arrives at the gonadotrophs (in the anterior pituitary), it stimulates the release of gonadotrophins, luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), into the systemic circulation. Then, gonadotrophins stimulate the gonads to release testosterone in males and oestradiol in female.

Additionally, kisspeptin signalling also occurs at extrahypothalamic brain regions, where first clues for its role in sexual and emotional processing were given (Popa et al., 2008).

4.4.2 Material and Methods:

Kisspeptin is thought to be non-stable in serum, since its short-term degradation has been reported in several manufacturers' instructions of a wide range of ELISA kits. Indeed, UGR tested kiss 1 in two occasions in serum samples, with poor results.

As the stability of this protein could be based on the number of amino acids in its chain, UGR thought that it would be easier to find measurable levels of this neuropeptide if focusing on kiss 54, given its length. Recently, a study developed by Gorkem et al., (2017) (Gorkem et al., 2018) measured KISS 54 with an ELISA Kit from MyBioSource (Catalog# MBS3804716) and UGR has made the first trial, shown in this report.

The main goal of this experiment was to detect levels of kisspeptin 54 in serum samples and to assess to which extent the age of the sample can influence KISS54 stability. To pursue these goals, UGR tested two sets of serum samples (10 samples each) with different times of conservation:

- 10 fresh serum samples with less than 24 hours
- 10 frozen serum samples that have been kept at -20 °C during more than one year.

Protocol

Samples characteristics:

Very briefly, 10 serum samples just taken from the hospital with less than 24 hours (<24 h) were aliquoted into 1.5 mL eppendorfs and were immediately tested. Additionally, 10 serum samples that have been kept at -20°C for more than 1 year (>1 y) were defrosted and tested.

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ELISA Kit procedure:

1. 2. Take out kit and samples and leave them to reach room temperature (25 minutes)
3. 4. Make Wash Buffer (x20): Dilute it 20 times: 25 mL were mixed into 475 mL of distilled water
5. 6. Follow manufacturer's instructions
7. 8. According to plate set-up, add: 50 μ L of standards
9. 10. According to plate set-up, add: 10 μ L of samples
11. 12. Add 40 μ L of sample diluent to wells with samples (which means that samples are diluted 5 times)
13. 14. Do not add any reagent into the Blk wells
15. 16. Add 100 μ L of HRP-Conjugate to each well
17. 18. Seal the plate, and incubate for 60 minutes at 37°C
19. 20. Wash plate by adding 400 μ L of Wash Buffer to each well. Repeat 5 times
21. 22. Add 50 μ L of chromagen solution A and 50 μ L of chromagen solution B. Mix gently
23. 24. Incubate during 15 minutes at 37 °C. Protect from light
25. 26. Add 50 μ L of Stop Solution per well
27. 28. Within 15 minutes, use the microplate reader at O.D. 450 nm

In the **Figure 17**, a graphical procedure depicting each step taken in the protocol of the ELISA Kit is shown.

Figure 17: ELISA sandwich-based approach. Graphical description of the steps mentioned in the protocol section

Plate set-up

The plate set-up is showed in the figure below (**Figure 18**).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BLK	BLK	F1	F5	F9	T3	T7					
B	BLK	BLK	F1	F5	F9	T3	T7					
C	4000 pg/mL	4000 pg/mL	F2	F6	F10	T4	T8					
D	2000 pg/mL	2000 pg/mL	F2	F6	F10	T4	T8					
E	1000 pg/mL	1000 pg/mL	F3	F7	T1	T5	T9					
F	500 pg/mL	500 pg/mL	F3	F7	T1	T5	T9					
G	250 pg/mL	250 pg/mL	F4	F8	T2	T6	T10					
H	0 pg/mL	0 pg/mL	F4	F8	T2	T6	T10					

Figure 18: Plate set-up for testing KISS 54 in serum samples with different times of conservation

In blue, internal standards.

F= Fresh samples with less than 24 hours (green)

T= Frozen samples kept at -20°C for more than one year (orange)

4.4.3 KISS54 Results:

Table 7 shows the **raw absorbance** detected (only wells with samples or standards will be showed, which were in rows 1 to 7):

Table 7: Raw absorbance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
A	0,052	0,05	0,096	0,174	0,151	0,161	0,148
B	0,049	0,048	0,104	0,176	0,147	0,161	0,155
C	1,139	1,1	0,156	0,13	0,138	0,152	0,139
D	0,577	0,491	0,152	0,13	0,124	0,158	0,119
E	0,328	0,266	0,142	0,14	0,157	0,206	0,141
F	0,17	0,156	0,049	0,161	0,152	0,203	0,136
G	0,108	0,109	0,153	0,134	0,207	0,163	0,171
H	0,05	0,051	0,188	0,138	0,205	0,15	0,161

Substrate solution B was not added to well F3 (showed in red). Thus, no absorbance was caught by the luminometer (450nm)

Table 8: Calibration Curve

Concent. (pg/ml)			Corrected-Blk		Media	SD
BLK	0,04975					
4000	1,139	1,1	1,08925	1,05025	1,06975	0,02757716
2000	0,577	0,491	0,52725	0,44125	0,48425	0,06081118
1000	0,328	0,266	0,27825	0,21625	0,24725	0,04384062
500	0,17	0,156	0,12025	0,10625	0,11325	0,00989949
250	0,108	0,156	0,05825	0,10625	0,08225	0,03394113
0	0,05	0,051	0,00025	0,00125	0,00075	0,00070711

In the first row, internal standard concentrations (pg/mL) are shown. Second and third rows showed the absorbance; fourth and fifth the correction by mean blank absorbance and sixth and seventh de mean and standard deviation (SD) of the absorbance, respectively.

In the figure below (**Figure 18**), a graph showing the calibration curve with the internal standards, the equation of the slope and the R^2 , needed to interpolate and calculate the concentrations of KISS 54 in serum samples.

Figure 18: Calibration Curve with the internal standards, the slope equation and the R²

As an additional quality control, the intra assay coefficient of variability (%) was calculated, getting a total CV of 4.1 % and all samples-specific CVs were below 15 %, the recommended CV for all ELISA assays. **Table 10** shows the concentrations of KISS54 found in serum samples.

Table 9: Intra assay coefficient of variation (CV)

Samples abs		Mean	SD	CV(%)	
F1	0,096 0,104	0,1	0,00565685	5,65685425	
F2	0,156 0,152	0,154	0,00282843	1,83664099	
F3	0,142 0,142	0,142			
F4	0,153 0,188	0,1705	0,02474874	14,5153885	
F5	0,174 0,176	0,175	0,00141421	0,80812204	
F6	0,13 0,13	0,13	0	0	
F7	0,14 0,161	0,1505	0,01484924	9,86660625	
F8	0,134 0,138	0,136	0,00282843	2,07972583	
F9	0,151 0,147	0,149	0,00282843	1,89827324	
F10	0,138 0,124	0,131	0,00989949	7,55686636	
T1	0,157 0,152	0,1545	0,00353553	2,28837146	
T2	0,207 0,205	0,206	0,00141421	0,68651144	
T3	0,161 0,161	0,161	0	0	
T4	0,152 0,158	0,155	0,00424264	2,73718754	
T5	0,206 0,203	0,2045	0,00212132	1,03732046	
T6	0,163 0,15	0,1565	0,00919239	5,87373045	
T7	0,148 0,155	0,1515	0,00494975	3,26716005	
T8	0,139 0,119	0,129	0,01414214	10,9628958	
T9	0,141 0,136	0,1385	0,00353553	2,55273206	
T10	0,171 0,161	0,166	0,00707107	4,2596794	
				Total CV(%)	4,09916137

Table 10: Concentrations of KISS 54 in serum samples

	Samples abs		Blk-corrected		Formula $x = (y/0,0003) + 0,0157$		Dilution factor (x5)		Mean (pg/mL)	SD	Mean (ng/mL)	SD
	F1	0,096	0,104	0,04625	0,05425	154,18	180,85	770,91	904,25	837,58	94,2809042	0,8375785
F2	0,156	0,152	0,10625	0,10225	354,18	340,85	1770,91	1704,25	1737,58	47,1404521	1,7375785	0,04714045
F3	0,142	0,049	0,09225	-0,00075	307,52		1537,58		1537,58		1,5375785	
F4	0,153	0,188	0,10325	0,13825	344,18	460,85	1720,91	2304,25	2012,58	412,478956	2,0125785	0,41247896
F5	0,174	0,176	0,12425	0,12625	414,18	420,85	2070,91	2104,25	2087,58	23,570226	2,0875785	0,02357023
F6	0,13	0,13	0,08025	0,08025	267,52	267,52	1337,58	1337,58	1337,58	0	1,3375785	0
F7	0,14	0,161	0,09025	0,11125	300,85	370,85	1504,25	1854,25	1679,25	247,487373	1,67924517	0,24748737
F8	0,134	0,138	0,08425	0,08825	280,85	294,18	1404,25	1470,91	1437,58	47,1404521	1,4375785	0,04714045
F9	0,151	0,147	0,10125	0,09725	337,52	324,18	1687,58	1620,91	1654,25	47,1404521	1,65424517	0,04714045
F10	0,138	0,124	0,08825	0,07425	294,18	247,52	1470,91	1237,58	1354,25	164,991582	1,35424517	0,16499158
T1	0,157	0,152	0,10725	0,10225	357,52	340,85	1787,58	1704,25	1745,91	58,9255651	1,74591183	0,05892557
T2	0,207	0,205	0,15725	0,15525	524,18	517,52	2620,91	2587,58	2604,25	23,570226	2,60424517	0,02357023
T3	0,161	0,161	0,11125	0,11125	370,85	370,85	1854,25	1854,25	1854,25	0	1,85424517	0
T4	0,152	0,158	0,10225	0,10825	340,85	360,85	1704,25	1804,25	1754,25	70,7106781	1,75424517	0,07071068
T5	0,206	0,203	0,15625	0,15325	520,85	510,85	2604,25	2554,25	2579,25	35,3553391	2,57924517	0,03535534
T6	0,163	0,15	0,11325	0,10025	377,52	334,18	1887,58	1670,91	1779,25	153,206469	1,77924517	0,15320647
T7	0,148	0,155	0,09825	0,10525	327,52	350,85	1637,58	1754,25	1695,91	82,4957911	1,69591183	0,08249579
T8	0,139	0,119	0,08925	0,06925	297,52	230,85	1487,58	1154,25	1320,91	235,70226	1,32091183	0,23570226
T9	0,141	0,136	0,09125	0,08625	304,18	287,52	1520,91	1437,58	1479,25	58,9255651	1,47924517	0,05892557
T10	0,171	0,161	0,12125	0,11125	404,18	370,85	2020,91	1854,25	1937,58	117,85113	1,9375785	0,11785113

Abs = absorbance; Blk = blank; SD = Standard deviation.

In green colour serum samples of less than 24 hours are shown, while in orange, serum samples kept at -20 °C during more than one year are shown.

A histogram showing the distribution of KISS 54 levels across all samples is shown in **Figure 20**. Mean (SD) of KISS 54 detected in 20 serum samples was 1.72 (± 0.4) ng/mL.

Figure 20: Histogram showing the distribution of serum KISS 54 in 20 samples (fresh and frozen samples)

In order to assess if differences of KISS 54 levels were found between serum sets, a frequency analysis was performed in SPSS. **Table 11** shows the summary of KISS 54 levels in frozen samples (>1 y), fresh samples (<24 h) and both. Frozen and fresh samples were not from the same individuals.

Table 11: Cases summary of KISS 54 serum levels

Cases Summary						
KISS54						
Sample type	N	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max
Frozen samples (>1y)	10	1,8751	0,13200	1,7667	1,32	2,60
Fresh samples (<24h)	10	1,5676	0,11384	1,5959	0,84	2,09
Total	20	1,7213	0,09187	1,7167	0,84	2,60

Range of KISS 58 levels were 0.84 (minimum) and 2.60 (maximum).

Mean (SD) serum KISS 54 levels were 1.88 ng/mL and 1.57 ng/mL in frozen samples and fresh samples, respectively.

In order to further assess potential differences between serum sets, a box-plot graphic was performed (see **Figure 21**). P50 (P25; P75) levels of KISS 54 in 24 h-serum group and one-year-serum group were 1.6 (1.4; 1.8) and 1.8 (1.6; 2.1) ng/mL, respectively.

Figure 21: Serum levels distribution of KISS 54 in 24 h-serum groups(n=10) VS one-year-serum group (n=10)

Distribution of serum KISS54 concentrations in 105 adolescents from the INMA-Granada:

Following this protocol, serum kisspeptin-54 levels were assessed in 105 adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort to better assess the precision and range of measurements. As shown in Figure 22, serum Kiss-54 was detected in all samples which had been stored at -80°C during the last two years. The intra- and inter-assay CVs were 2.9% and 3.8%, respectively. These results support the stability of serum Kiss-54 up to two years of storage. Although Kiss-54 was detected in all samples, levels are probably higher in female than male teenagers as previously reported (Zhu et al., 2016).

Figure 22: Serum levels of KISS 54 from male adolescents of the INMA-Granada cohort (n=105)

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4.4.4 Conclusion

In this trial, KISS 54 was successfully detected in serum samples from both groups, 24 h-fresh serum samples and one-year-serum samples. A priori, there were no significant differences between groups; however, it seems that KISS 54 levels are slightly higher in one-year-serum group, which could mean that the stability of KISS 54 is good enough to measure it in the aligned studies from the HBM4EU project. Additionally, serum KISS 54 levels were successfully measured in approximately 100 adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort, showing a good distribution. Although we did not assess adolescent girls, KISS 54 levels are normally a bit higher in females, so we do not expect problems quantifying KISS 54 protein levels in adolescent girls from the aligned studies. The next step is to assess the prediction and mediation power of this neuropeptide in exposure-effects associations in the INMA-Granada cohort to provide additional details on its physiological validity.

4.5 Classic hormonal and metabolic parameters (UGR)

For all effect biomarkers, and especially for classic hormonal markers, the age of the study population will be considered, especially in the case of hormonal parameters, since the reference range of measurements should be adapted for each group (children, adolescents or adults). This aspect will affect mainly, but not only, to some of the selected classical biomarkers. Moreover, to guarantee the lowest possible variability in the measurements, other aspects such as operators, season and temperature, will be also be taken into account. For example, all samples in the HBM4EU aligned studies will be frozen samples. For that reason in the statistical analyses the influence of this variable (number of years, -80 or -20 storage) will be tested. All analyses will be performed automatically using an auto-analyser.

CREATININE

Creatinine measurement is done through the CRJ2U Test. It is a colorimetric kinetic test based on the Jaffé method. In an alkaline solution, creatinine forms a reddish-yellow complex with picrate. The dye formation rate is proportional to the creatinine concentration in the sample.

Calibration

Calibration mode: Linear regression

Calibration replica: Duplicate

Calibration interval: every 7 days

Quality control:

- Reference range: Precinorm PUC
- Pathological interval: Precipath PUC
- Control interval: Every 24 hours and check after calibration

Limits and intervals

- Measuring range: 0.027-32.5 mmol / L (0.31-367 mg / dL)

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Determine the samples with higher concentrations through the repeat function. With the repeat function, samples are diluted 1: 4. Results for samples diluted by the repeat cycle function are automatically multiplied by the factor of 4.

- Lower limits of measurement:

Lower detection limit of the test: 0.027 mmol / L (0.31 mg / dL)

The lower limit of detection represents the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the concentration 3 standard deviations above the zero sample (zero sample + 3 SD, repeatability, n = 30).

Precision

Precision was determined using human samples and controls according to internal protocol with intermediate precision and repeatability (2 aliquots per series, 2 series per day, 20 days). The following results were obtained:

Table 12: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for CRJ2U Test

	Level 1	Level 2
Median	2.16 mmol/L (24.4 mg/dL)	19.1 mmol /L (216 mg/dL)
CV repeatability	1.4%	0.8%
CV intermediate precision	2.5%	1.6%

Analysis limitations – interferences

- Test: recovery in the decisive creatinine range for adults (20 mmol / L in urine) within $\pm 10\%$ of baseline.
- Icterus: no significant interference up to a bilirubin concentration of 855 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ (50 mg/dL).
- Hemolysis: no significant interference up to a hemoglobin concentration of 683 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ (1100 mg/dL).
- Glucose: no significant interference up to a glucose concentration of 117 mmol / L (2,100 mg/dL).
- Urobilinogen: no significant interference up to an urobilinogen concentration of 676 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ (40 mg/dL).
- Drugs: No interference was recorded with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations. Exception: Hydroxocobalamin (Cyanokit) may cause artificially low results.
- Test: recovery within $\pm 10\%$ of baseline at a creatinine concentration of 2500 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ (28.3 mg/dL).

Urea: no significant interference up to a urea concentration of 2100 mmol / L (12612 mg/dL). A high concentration of homogentisic acid causes false results in urine samples.

Ketone bodies can cause artificially high results in urine.

In unusual cases, false results may be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström's macroglobulinemia). If the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) is estimated according to the Schwartz formula, falsely elevated results may be obtained. For diagnosis, test results should always be interpreted taking into account the patient's anamnesis, clinical examination as well as the results of other examinations.

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THYROXINE (T4)

In the Elecsys FT4 III test, the concentration of free thyroxine is determined with a ruthenium chelate-labeled anti-T4 antibody (Tris (2,2'-bipyridine) ruthenium (II) chelate (Ru (bpy))).

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform calibration once per batch with fresh reagents from a reagent kit registered at most 24 hours before on the analyser.

Repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same batch of reagents
- after 7 days (if the same reagent kit is used in the analyser)
- if necessary: for example, if the quality control values are outside the defined range

Quality control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Additionally other appropriate controls can be used.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.5-100 pmol / L (defined by the Limit of Detection and the maximum of the main curve). Values below the Limit of Detection are reported as <0.5 pmol / L. Values above the measurement range are reported as > 100 pmol / L.
- Lower limits of measurement
- Limit of Blank = 0.3 pmol / L
- Detection Limit = 0.5 pmol / L
- Limit of Quantification = 1.3 pmol / L
- The Limit of Blank, the Limit of Detection and the Limit of Quantification were determined in compliance with the EP17 - A2 requirements of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). The Limit of Detection is determined based on the Limit of Blank and the standard deviation of low concentration samples. The Limit of Detection corresponds to the lowest detectable analyte concentration (value higher than the Limit of Blank with a probability of 95%).

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, samples and controls according to a protocol (EP05-A3) of the CLS (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 2 daily cycles in duplicate, each for 21 days (n = 84). The following results were obtained:

Table 13: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys FT4 III test

Sample	Median (pmol/L)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (pmol/L)	CV %	DE (pmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	1.55	0.089	5.7	0.166	10.7
Human serum 2	13.6	0.239	1.8	0.475	3.5
Human serum 3	23.9	0.411	1.7	0.729	3.0
Human serum 4	57.8	1.11	1.9	2.26	3.9
Human serum 5	92.0	2.24	2.4	5.44	5.9
PreciControl U1	15.8	0.258	1.6	0.474	3.0
PreciControl U2	41.0	0.867	2.1	1.39	3.4

Analysis limitations - interferences

The effects of the following endogenous substances and the following pharmaceutical compounds on the performance of the test were analysed without any interference being observed.

Table 14: Limitations and interferences of the Elecsys FT4 III test

Substance	Concentration analysed
Bilirubin	≤ 701 µmol/L or ≤ 41 mg/dL
Hemoglobin	≤ 0.621 mmol/L or ≤ 1000 mg/dL
Intralipid	≤ 2000 mg/dL
Biotin	≤ 409 nmol/L or ≤ 1000 ng/mL
Rheumatoid factors	≤ 1200 UI/mL
IgG	≤ 7 g/dL
IgA	≤ 1.6 g/dL
IgM	≤ 1 g/dL

THYROTROPIN (TSH)

For the determination of thyrotropin, the Elecsys TSH test is used. This test uses monoclonal antibodies specifically directed against human TSH.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform calibration once per batch with fresh reagents from a reagent kit registered at most 24 hours before on the analyser.

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The calibration interval can be extended if the laboratory can ensure an acceptable verification of the calibration.

Repeat the calibration:

- after 8 weeks if it is the same batch of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit in the analyser)
- if necessary: for example, if the quality control values are outside the defined range

Quality Control

Perform quality control with PreciControl Universal, PreciControl TSH or PreciControl Thyro Sensitive.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.005-100 $\mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$ (defined by the lower limit of detection and the maximum of the master curve). The functional sensitivity is 0.014 $\mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$. Values below the lower limit of detection are reported as $<0.005 \mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$. Values above the measurement range are indicated as $> 100 \mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$, or diluted by a factor of 10, respectively up to 1000 $\mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$.
- Lower limits of measurement
Lower limit of detection: 0.005 $\mu\text{IU} / \text{mL}$
The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero.

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a mixture of human serum and controls in a modified protocol (EP5-A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days ($n = 60$); Repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, $n = 21$. PreciControl TSH was determined once a day for 10 days ($n = 10$). The following results were obtained:

Table 15: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys TSH test

Sample	Median ($\mu\text{IU}/\text{mL}$)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE ($\mu\text{IU}/\text{mL}$)	CV %	DE ($\mu\text{IU}/\text{mL}$)	CV %
Human serum 1	0.034	0.003	8.6	0.003	8.7
Human serum 2	0.91	0.02	2.1	0.03	3.3
Human serum 3	3.96	0.07	1.8	0.14	3.6
PreciControl Universal 1	2.45	0.05	1.9	0.05	2.2
PreciControl Universal 2	10.67	0.16	1.5	0.19	1.8

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Analysis limitations - interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <701 µmol / L or <41 mg / dL), hemolysis (Hb <0.621 mmol / L or <1 g / dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1500 mg / dL), or biotin (<102 nmol / L or <25 ng / mL), IgG <2 g / dL and IgM <0.5 g / dL.

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg / day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

No interference from rheumatoid factors (up to 3250 IU / mL) or in samples from dialysis patients has been observed.

The prozone effect (high dose hook) has not been recorded with TSH concentrations up to 1000 µIU / mL.

26 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding any interference.

The presence of autoantibodies can induce the formation of high molecular weight complexes (macro-TSH) causing unexpectedly high levels of TSH. In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference. These effects have been minimised thanks to a suitable test design.

TRIYODOTHYRONINE (T3)

The Elecsys T3 test is based on the competition principle and uses a specific polyclonal antibody directed against T3. Endogenous T3, released by the action of 8-anilino-1-naphthalenesulfonic acid (ANS), competes with the biotinylated derivative of exogenously added T3 to occupy binding sites on antibodies labeled with ruthenium complex (Tris Complex (2,2'-bipyridine) ruthenium (II) (Ru (bpy))).

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform calibration once per batch with fresh reagents from a reagent kit registered at most 24 hours before on the analyser.

The calibration interval can be extended if the laboratory can ensure an acceptable verification of the calibration.

It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 8 weeks if it is the same batch of reagents
- after 7 days (if the same reagent kit is used in the analyser)
- if necessary: for example, if the quality control values are outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

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Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.300-10.0 nmol / L or 0.195-6.51 ng / mL (defined by the lower limit of detection and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the limit of detection are reported as <0.300 nmol / L (<0.195 ng / mL). Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 10.0 nmol / L or > 6.51 ng / mL.
- Lower limits of measurement
Lower limit of detection: 0.300 nmol / L or 0.195 ng / mL
The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable analyte concentration that can be distinguished from 0.

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a mixture of human serum and controls in a modified protocol (EP5-A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days (n = 60); Repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, n = 21. The following results have been obtained:

Analysis limitations - interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <599 µmol / L or <35 mg / dL), hemolysis (Hb <1.2 mmol / L or <2.0 g / dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1800 mg / dL) or biotin (<123 nmol / L or <30 ng / mL).

Test: recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg / day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

No interference from rheumatoid factors (up to 1500 IU / mL) or in samples from dialysis patients has been observed.

26 commonly used drugs were tested in vitro without finding any interference with this assay.

Treatment with amiodarone can cause a reduction in T3 values.

Phenytoin, phenylbutazone and salicylates cause the release of T3 from binding proteins, reducing the total hormonal level of T3 with normal concentrations of fT3. Anti-thyroid hormone autoantibodies may interfere with the assay.

Alterations in transporter proteins due to, for example, familial dysalbuminaemic hyperthyroxinemia (FDH) can lead to values other than theoretical, which is characteristic of this disorder.

If the concentrations of the binding proteins (TBG, albumin) are pathological, the levels of total T3 may be outside the normal range, even if the metabolic state is euthyroid, as happens for example in patients with non-thyroid diseases, pregnant or due to ingestion of contraceptives. In such cases, it is recommended to determine the concentrations of fT3 or fT4.

In isolated cases, interference may occur due to extremely high titers of antibodies directed against antibodies. Specific to the analyte, streptavidin or ruthenium. These effects have been minimised thanks to a suitable test design.

Table 16: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys T3 test

Sample	Median (ng/mL)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (ng/mL)	CV %	DE (ng/mL)	CV %
Human serum 1	0.79	0.03	3.6	0.05	5.4
Human serum 2	1.87	0.08	4.2	0.14	4.7
Human serum 3	3.31	0.18	5.3	0.27	5.4
PreciControl Univ 1	1.38	0.06	4.1	0.10	4.8
PreciControl Univ 2	4.11	0.14	3.5	0.26	4.1

TOTAL TESTOSTERONE (TT)

The Elecsys Testosterone II test is an in vitro immunological test for the quantitative determination of testosterone in human serum and plasma. The Elecsys Testosterone II test is based on a competitive test principle that uses a high affinity sheep monoclonal antibody directed against testosterone. Endogenous testosterone released from the sample by 2-bromoestradiol competes with the added testosterone derivative labeled with a ruthenium chelate (a) for the binding sites of the biotinylated antibody.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.025-15.0 ng / mL or 0.087-52.0 nmol / L (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <0.025 ng / mL or <0.087 nmol / L. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 15.0 ng / mL (> 52.0 nmol / L).
- Lower limits of measurement:
 Limit of Blank = 0.012 ng / mL or 0.042 nmol / L
 Limit of Detection = 0.025 ng / mL or 0.087 nmol / L
 Limit of Quantification = 0.120 ng / mL or 0.416 nmol / L

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Both the Limit of Blank and the Limit of Detection were determined complying with the requirements established in protocol EP17-A of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute).

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, samples and controls according to a protocol (EP5 - A2) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 2 daily cycles in duplicate, each for 21 days (n = 84). The following results were obtained:

Table 17: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys Testosterone II test

		Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
Sample	Median (ng/mL)	DE (ng/mL)	CV %	DE (ng/mL)	CV %
Human serum 1	0.095	0.004	4.7	0.008	8.4
Human serum 2	0.691	0.014	2.1	0.022	3.2
Human serum 3	2.16	0.042	1.9	0.060	2.8
Human serum 4	8.67	0.229	2.6	0.243	2.8
Human serum 5	13.0	0.158	1.2	0.440	3.4
PreciControl U1	6.30	0.088	1.4	0.182	2.9
PreciControl U2	2.65	0.047	1.8	0.097	3.7

Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <513 µmol / L or <30 mg / dL), hemolysis (Hb <0.372 mmol / L or <0.600 g / dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1000 mg / dL), or biotin (<123 nmol / L or <30 ng / mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of baseline (concentration range > 1-15 ng / mL), recovery within ± 15% of baseline (concentration range > 0.5-1 ng / mL), and recovery of ± 0.075 ng / mL (0.150-0.500 ng / mL concentration range).

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg / day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 1000 IU / mL.

18 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences. Two special drugs were further analysed. A strong interaction with nandrolone (International Non-Patented Name, WHO) was recorded. Do not use samples from patients receiving nandrolone.

In isolated cases, elevated testosterone levels may be seen in female patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD).

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

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ESTRADIOL (E2)

The Elecsys Estradiol III test is an electrochemiluminescence immunoassay based on a competitive test principle using two monoclonal antibodies specifically directed against 17 β -estradiol. Endogenous estradiol released from the sample by mestrolone competes with the added derivative of estradiol labeled with the ruthenium chelate for the binding sites of the biotinylated antibody.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 18.4-11010 pmol/L or 5-3000 pg/mL (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <5 pg/mL or <18.4 pmol/L. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 3000 pg/mL (> 11010 pmol/L).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Limit of Blank = 3 pg/mL or 11 pmol/L
Limit of Detection = 5 pg/mL or 18.4 pmol/L
Limit of Quantification = 25 pg/mL or 91.8 pmol/L
Both the Limit of Blank and the Limit of Detection were determined complying with the requirements established in protocol EP17-A of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute).

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Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, samples and controls according to a protocol (EP5 - A2) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 2 daily cycles in duplicate, each for 21 days (n = 84). The following results were obtained:

Table 18: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys Estradiol III test

		Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
Sample	Median (pg/mL)	DE (pg/mL)	CV %	DE (pg/mL)	CV %
Human serum 1	25.4	2.16	8.5	3.03	11.9
Human serum 2	45.3	2.11	4.7	3.10	6.8
Human serum 3	165	5.14	3.1	5.55	3.4
Human serum 4	1368	26.6	1.9	34.1	2.5
Human serum 5	2932	68.9	2.4	80.9	2.8
PreciControl U1	86.1	2.99	3.5	3.83	4.5
PreciControl U2	413	13.0	3.2	14.6	3.5

Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <1129 µmol/L or <66 mg/dL), hemolysis (Hb <0.621 mmol/L or <1.0 g/dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1000 mg/dL), or biotin (<147 nmol/L or <36 ng/mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg / day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 1200 IU/mL.

17 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences.

Test results may be erroneous for samples from patients who have received vaccinations with rabbit sera or who have rabbits as pets.

To avoid the risk of cross-reactivity, do not use this test to monitor estradiol levels in patients treated with Fulvestrant.

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

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FOLLICLE STIMULATING HORMONE (FSH)

The Elecsys FSH test is an electrochemiluminescence immunoassay. This test uses two monoclonal antibodies directed specifically against human FSH. Cross-reactions with LH, TSH, hCG, hGH, and hPL are so minimal that they can be ignored.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.100-200 mUI/mL (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <0.100 mUI/mL. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 200 mUI/mL.
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: <0.100 mIU / mL

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the concentration 2 standard deviations above the lowest standard (master calibrator, standard 1 + 2 SD, repeatability study, n = 21).

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a mixture of human serum and controls in a modified protocol (EP5-A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days (n = 60); repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, n = 21. The following results were obtained:

Table 19: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys FSH test

Sample	Median (mUI/mL)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (mUI/mL)	CV %	DE (mUI/mL)	CV %
Human serum 1	1.2	0.02	1.8	0.06	5.3
Human serum 2	50.4	0.74	1.5	1.90	3.8
Human serum 3	103	1.85	1.8	5.24	5.1
PreciControl U1	11.1	0.22	2.0	0.41	3.7
PreciControl U2	28.9	0.40	1.4	0.85	2.9

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Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <1094 µmol/L or <64 mg/dL), hemolysis (Hb <0.621 mmol/L or <1.0 g/dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1900 mg/dL), or biotin (<246 nmol/L or <60 ng/mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg/day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 2250 IU/mL.

17 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences.

The prozone effect (high dose hook) has not been recorded with FSH concentrations up to 2000 mIU/mL.

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

LUTEINIZING HORMONE (LH)

The Elecsys LH test is an electrochemiluminescence immunoassay. This test uses monoclonal antibodies directed specifically against human LH. The two specific antibodies used are capable of recognising particular conformations, that is, the biotinylated antibody recognises an epitope made up of the two subunits, while the ruthenium-chelated antibody a) recognises an epitope found on the β subunit. For this reason, the Elecsys LH test's cross-reactions to FSH, TSH, hCG, hGH, and hPL are so minimal that they can be ignored.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.100-200 mUI/mL (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <0.100 mUI/mL. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 200 mUI/mL.
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.100 mIU / mL

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the concentration 2 standard deviations above the lowest standard (master calibrator, standard 1 + 2 SD, repeatability study, n = 21).

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Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a mixture of human serum and controls in a modified protocol (EP5-A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days (n = 60); repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, n = 21. The following results were obtained:

Table 20: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys LH test

Sample	Median (mUI/mL)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (mUI/mL)	CV %	DE (mUI/mL)	CV %
Human serum 1	0.54	0.01	1.8	0.03	5.2
Human serum 2	27.2	0.21	0.8	0.54	2.0
Human serum 3	50.7	0.41	0.8	1.01	2.0
PreciControl U1	9.38	0.11	1.1	0.19	2.0
PreciControl U2	44.8	0.42	0.9	0.83	1.9

Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <1129 µmol/L or <66 mg/dL), hemolysis (Hb <0.621 mmol/L or <1.0 g/dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1900 mg/dL), or biotin (<205 nmol/L or <50 ng/mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg/day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 1500 IU/mL.

17 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences.

Neonate samples have not been tested with the Elecsys LH test.

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

SEX HORMONE TRANSPORTER GLOBULIN (SHBG)

The Elecsys SHBG test is an electrochemiluminescence immunoassay. This test uses two monoclonal antibodies directed specifically against human SHBG.

Cross-reactivity with the following substances is irrelevant: α1-fetoprotein (AFP), corticosteroid-binding globulin (CBG), DHT, estradiol, fibrinogen, human immunoglobulin A (IgA), human immunoglobulin G (IgG), plasminogen, human-binding globulin thyroxine (TBG), testosterone, thyroglobulin (Tg), transferrin, and thyrotropin (TSH).

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Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.350-200 nmol/L (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <0.350 nmol/L. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 200 nmol/L.
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.350 nmol/L

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the concentration 2 standard deviations above the lowest standard (master calibrator, standard 1 + 2 SD, repeatability study, n = 21).

Precision

Precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a mixture of human serum and controls in a modified protocol (EP5-A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days (n = 60); repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, n = 21. The following results were obtained:

Table 21: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys SHBG test

Sample	Median (nmol/L)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (nmol/L)	CV %	DE (nmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	14.1	0.30	2.1	0.39	2.7
Human serum 2	44.2	1.05	2.4	1.24	2.8
Human serum 3	204	5.61	2.7	11.4	5.6
PreciControl U1	34.9	0.76	2.2	0.92	2.6
PreciControl U2	19.0	0.41	2.2	0.52	2.7

Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <1026 µmol/L or <60 mg/dL), hemolysis (Hb <1.8 mmol/L or <2.9 g/dL), lipemia (Intralipid <2700 mg/dL), or biotin (<246 nmol/L or <60 ng/mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value.

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In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg/day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 1160 IU/mL.

16 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences.

The prozone effect (high dose hook) has not been recorded with SHBG concentrations up to 1000 nmol / L.

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

TOTAL CHOLESTEROL (TC)

The CHOL2 test is a colorimetric enzymatic method.

Cholesterol esters are split by the action of cholesterol esterase to free cholesterol and fatty acids. Cholesterol oxidase then catalyses the oxidation of cholesterol to cholest-4-en-3-one and hydrogen peroxide. In the presence of peroxidase, the hydrogen peroxide formed produces an oxidative bond of phenol and 4-aminophenazone to form a quinoneimine red dye.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform Two-Point Calibration:

- with each lot of reagents
- if necessary according to quality control procedures

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl ClinChem Multi.

Adapt control ranges and limits to individual laboratory requirements. Results must be within defined limits.

Each laboratory should establish corrective measures to follow in case the values are outside the defined limits.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.1-20.7 mmol/L (3.86-800mg/dL).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.1 mmol/L (3.86 mg/dL).

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable analyte concentration that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the value 3 standard deviations above the lowest standard (standard 1 + 3 SD, repeatability, n = 21).

Precision

Precision was determined using human samples and controls according to an internal protocol with repeatability (n = 21) and intermediate precision (3 aliquots per series, 1 series per day, 21 days). The following results were obtained:

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Table 22: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for CHOL2 test

Sample	Repeatability			Intermediate precision		
	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	2.85	0.03	1.1	1,07	0.03	1.6
Human serum 2	7.39	0.05	0.7	7.13	0.10	1.4
Precinorm U	2.29	0.02	1.1	2.31	0.04	1.6
Precipath U	4.74	0.04	0.9	4.85	0.08	1.6

Analysis limitations – interferences

Recovery within $\pm 10\%$ of baseline values with a cholesterol concentration of 5.2 mmol/L (200 mg/dL).

Icterus: No significant interference up to an index I of 16 for conjugated bilirubin and 14 for unconjugated bilirubin, which is equivalent to an approximate concentration of conjugated bilirubin of 274 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 16 mg / dL and an approximate concentration of unconjugated bilirubin 239 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 14 mg / dL.

Hemolysis: 17 No significant interference up to an index H of 700 (hemoglobin concentration: approximately 435 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 700 mg / dL).

Lipemia (Intralipid): No significant interferences up to the index L of 2000. There is no satisfactory correlation between the index L (which corresponds to turbidity) and the triglyceride concentration.

Drugs: No interference has been reported with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations.

Paracetamol poisoning is usually treated with N-acetylcysteine. Both N-acetylcysteine, used in therapeutic concentrations as an antidote, and the paracetamol metabolite, N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), can cause falsely low values.

Venipuncture should be done before administering metamizole. If venipuncture is performed immediately after or during administration of metamizole, falsely low results may be obtained.

In unusual cases, false results may be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström macroglobulinemia).

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HIGH-DENSITY LIPOPROTEIN CHOLESTEROL (HDL-C)

The HDLC3 test is a homogeneous enzymatic colorimetric test.

In the presence of magnesium ions, dextran sulfate forms water-soluble complexes selectively with LDL, VLDL, and chylomicrons resistant to PEG-modified enzymes.

The concentration of HDL cholesterol is determined enzymatically by cholesterol esterase and cholesterol oxidase coupled with PEG to the amine groups (approx. 40%).

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform Two-Point Calibration:

- with each lot of reagents
- if necessary according to quality control procedures

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl ClinChem Multi.

Adapt control ranges and limits to individual laboratory requirements. Results must be within defined limits.

Each laboratory should establish corrective measures to follow in case the values are outside the defined limits. The Laboratory Standardisation Panel (LSP) of the US Cholesterol Education Program recommends two levels of controls, one within the normal range (0.9-1.7 mmol / L or 35-65 mg / dL) and another close to it. at the decision concentration (<0.9 mmol / L or <35 mg / dL).

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.08-3.12 mmol/L (3-121mg/dL).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.08 mmol/L (3 mg/dL).

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable analyte concentration that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the value 3 standard deviations above the lowest standard (standard 1 + 3 SD, repeatability, n = 21).

Precision

Precision was determined using human samples and controls according to an internal protocol with repeatability (n = 21) and intermediate precision (3 aliquots per series, 1 series per day, 21 days). The following results were obtained:

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Table 23: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for HDLC3 test

Sample	Repeatability			Intermediate precision		
	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	1.20	0.01	0.6	1.17	0.01	0.9
Human serum 2	2.08	0.01	0.7	2.03	0.02	0.9
Precinorm L	1.38	0.01	0.4	1.34	0.01	0.9
Precipath HDL/LDL-C	0.89	0.01	1.0	0.88	0.01	1.5

Analysis limitations – interferences

Recovery within $\pm 10\%$ of baseline values with a cholesterol concentration of 1 mmol/L (38.7 mg/dL).

Icterus: No significant interference up to an index I of 30 for conjugated bilirubin and 60 for unconjugated bilirubin, which is equivalent to an approximate concentration of conjugated bilirubin of 2513 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ or 30 mg / dL and an approximate concentration of unconjugated bilirubin 1026 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ or 60 mg/dL.

Hemolysis: 17 No significant interference up to an index H of 1200 (hemoglobin concentration: approximately 745 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ or 1200 mg / dL).

Lipemia (Intralipid): No significant interferences up to the index L of 1800. No interference from native triglycerides up to 13.7 mmol / L (1200 mg / dL). There is no satisfactory correlation between the index L (corresponding to turbidity) and the triglyceride concentration.

Others: High concentrations of free fatty acids and denatured proteins can cause falsely elevated HDL cholesterol values.

In isolated cases, elevated immunoglobulin levels can provide falsely elevated HDL cholesterol results. Ascorbic acid concentrations up to 2.84 mmol / L (50 mg / dL) do not interfere with the test.

Drugs: No interference has been reported with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations.

Paracetamol poisoning is usually treated with N-acetylcysteine. Both N-acetylcysteine, used in therapeutic concentrations as an antidote, and the paracetamol metabolite, N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), can cause falsely low values.

Venipuncture should be performed prior to administering metamizole. If venipuncture is performed immediately after or during administration of metamizole, falsely low results may be obtained.

In unusual cases, false results can be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström macroglobulinemia).

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LOW-DENSITY LIPOPROTEIN CHOLESTEROL (LDL-C)

The LDLC3 test is a homogeneous enzymatic colorimetric test.

Cholesterol esters and free cholesterol in LDL are measured by an enzymatic method using cholesterol esterase and cholesterol oxidase in the presence of surfactants that selectively solubilize LDL.

Enzymatic reactions with the other lipoproteins are inhibited by surfactants and a sugar compound. HDL, VLDL and chylomicron cholesterol is not determined.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform Two-Point Calibration:

- with each lot of reagents
- if necessary according to quality control procedures

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl ClinChem Multi.

Adapt control ranges and limits to individual laboratory requirements. Results must be within defined limits.

Each laboratory should establish corrective measures to follow in case the values are outside the defined limits.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.10-14.2 mmol/L (3.87-549mg/dL).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Limit of Blank = 0.10 mmol / L (3.87 mg / dL)
Detection Limit = 0.10 mmol / L (3.87 mg / dL)
Limit of Quantification = 0.10 mmol / L (3.87 mg / dL)

The Limit of Detection is determined based on the Limit of Blank and the standard deviation of low concentration samples. The Limit of Detection corresponds to the lowest concentration of detectable analyte (value above the Limit of Blank with a probability of 95%).

Precision

Repeatability and intermediate precision were determined with human samples and controls according to the EP5 guideline of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) with 4 aliquots per run, 1 run per day, for 21 days. The following results have been obtained:

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Table 24: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for LDLC3 test

Sample	Repeatability			Intermediate precision		
	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	0.302	0.004	1.2	0.316	0.008	2.5
Human serum 2	2.93	0.02	0.7	3.03	0.06	2.1
Human serum 3	7.83	0.06	0.7	8.14	0.16	1.9
Human serum 4	3.67	0.03	0.7	3.71	0.08	2.1
Human serum 5	13.6	0.10	0.8	13.7	0.3	2.0
Precinorm L	2.69	0.02	0.7	2.69	0.06	2.3
Precipath HDL/LDL-C	4.93	0.03	0.7	5.02	0.11	2.1

Analysis limitations – interferences

Test: recovery within ± 0.40 mmol / L of initial values for samples ≤ 4.0 mmol/L and within $\pm 10\%$ for samples > 4.0 mmol/L.

Icterus: no significant interference up to an index I of 60 for conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin (concentration of conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin: approximately 1026 μmol / L or 60 mg / dL).

Hemolysis: no significant interference up to an index H of 1000 (hemoglobin concentration: approximately 621 μmol /L or 1000 mg/dL).

Lipemia (Intralipid): no significant interferences up to the index L of 1000. There is no satisfactory correlation between the index L (which corresponds to turbidity) and the triglyceride concentration. No significant interference by HDL cholesterol (≤ 3.03 mmol / L or ≤ 117 mg / dL), VLDL-C (≤ 3.63 mmol / L or ≤ 140 mg / dL) or chylomicrons (≤ 22.6 mmol / L or ≤ 2000 mg / dL triglycerides).

Drugs: No interference has been recorded with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations. No interference from therapeutic concentrations of nicotinic acid (Niacin), statins (Simvastatin) and fibrates (Clofibrate).

Paracetamol poisoning is usually treated with N-acetylcysteine. Both N-acetylcysteine, used in therapeutic concentrations as an antidote, and the paracetamol metabolite, N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), can cause falsely low LDL-C values.

Venipuncture should be performed prior to administering metamizole. If venipuncture is performed immediately after or during administration of metamizole, falsely low results may be obtained.

Ascorbic acid concentrations up to 28.4 mmol / L (500 mg / dL) do not interfere with the test.

Liver dysfunction affects lipid metabolism; in these cases, the diagnostic value of HDL and LDL results is limited. In certain patients with liver dysfunction, the LDL cholesterol result shows a considerable negative deviation from the results obtained by beta-quantification.

In EDTA-treated plasma, values can be lowered compared to serum values.

In very rare cases, false results may be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström macroglobulinemia).

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GLUCOSE (GLUC)

The GLUC3 test is an ultraviolet radiation test. Enzymatic reference method using hexokinase.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform Two-Point Calibration:

- with each lot of reagents
- if necessary according to quality control procedures

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl ClinChem Multi.

Adapt control ranges and limits to individual laboratory requirements. Results must be within defined limits. Each laboratory should establish corrective measures to follow in case the values are outside the defined limits.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.11-41.6 mmol/L (2-750 mg/dL).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Limit of Blank = 0.11 mmol / L (2 mg/dL)
Detection Limit = 0.11 mmol / L (2 mg/dL)
Limit of Quantification = 0.11 mmol / L (2 mg/dL)

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable analyte concentration that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the value 3 standard deviations above the lowest standard (standard 1 + 3 SD, repeatability, n = 21).

Precision

Precision has been determined using human samples and controls according to an internal protocol. Serum / plasma: repeatability (n = 21), intermediate precision (3 aliquots per series, 1 series per day, 21 days).

Table 25: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for GLUC3 test

Sample	Repeatability			Intermediate precision		
	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	7.74	0.05	0.7	7.61	0.09	1.2
Human serum 2	5.41	0.04	0.7	5.28	0.06	1.1
Precinorm U	5.49	0.05	1.0	5.38	0.07	1.3
Precipath U	13.6	0.10	0.9	13.4	0.2	1.1

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Analysis limitations – interferences

Test: Recovery within $\pm 10\%$ of the initial value with a glucose concentration of 3.9 mmol/L (70.3 mg/dL).

Icterus: No significant interference up to an index I of 60 for conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin (concentration of conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin: approximately 1026 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 60 mg / dL).

Hemolysis: No significant interference up to an index H of 1000 (hemoglobin concentration: approximately 621 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 1000 mg / dL).

Lipemia (Intralipid): No significant interference up to the index L of 1000. There is no satisfactory correlation between the index L (which corresponds to turbidity) and the triglyceride concentration.

Drugs: No interference has been reported with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations.

In very rare cases, false results can be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström macroglobulinemia).

INSULIN (INS)

The Elecsys iNSULIN test is an electrochemiluminescence immunoassay. This test uses two monoclonal antibodies directed specifically against human insulin.

Calibration

Calibration interval: Carry out a batch calibration with fresh reagent (registered at most 24 hours before in the analyser). It is recommended to repeat the calibration:

- after 1 month (28 days) if it is the same lot of reagents
- after 7 days (when using the same reagent kit on the analyser)
- if necessary: p. ex. if the quality control is outside the defined range

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl Universal or PreciControl Multimarker.

Controls for the different concentration ranges should be carried out together with the test in single determinations at least once every 24 hours, with each reagent kit and after each calibration.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.2-1000 $\mu\text{U}/\text{mL}$ or 1.39-6945 pmol/L (defined by the detection limit and the maximum of the master curve). Values below the detection limit are reported as <1.39 pmol/L. Values above the limit of detection are reported as > 6945 pmol/L.
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.2 $\mu\text{U}/\text{mL}$ (1.39 pmol/L)

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable concentration of analyte that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the concentration 2 standard deviations above the lowest standard (master calibrator, standard 1 + 2 SD, repeatability study, n = 21).

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Precision

The precision has been determined using Elecsys reagents, a pool of human sera according to a modified protocol (EP5 - A) of the CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute): 6 times a day for 10 days (n = 60); repeatability on a MODULAR ANALYTICS E170 analyser, n = 21. The following results were obtained:

Table 26: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for Elecsys insulin test

Sample	Median (pmol/L)	Repeatability		Intermediate precision	
		DE (pmol/L)	CV %	DE (pmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	44.2	0.847	1.9	1.11	2.6
Human serum 2	145	2.71	1.9	4.10	2.8
Human serum 3	5188	105	2.0	129	2.5
PreciControl MM1	165	1.88	1.1	5.79	3.5
PreciControl MM2	567	7.92	1.4	21.1	3.7

Analysis limitations – interferences

The test is not affected by icterus (bilirubin <1539 µmol/L or <90 mg/dL), lipemia (Intralipid <1800 mg/dL), or biotin (<246 nmol/L or <60 ng/mL).

Test: Recovery within ± 10% of the initial value. Hemolysis interferes with the test.

In patients treated with high doses of biotin (> 5 mg/day), do not collect the sample before at least 8 hours after the last administration.

Rheumatoid factor interference has not been observed up to a concentration of 1890 IU/mL.

20 widely used drugs were tested in vitro without finding interferences.

The prozone effect (high dose hook) has not been recorded with insulin concentrations up to 138900 pmol / L.

Samples from patients treated with insulin of bovine, porcine or human origin may contain anti-insulin antibodies. This can influence the test results.

In isolated cases, extremely high titers of antibodies directed against specific antibodies to the analyte, streptavidin, or ruthenium may cause interference.

TRIGLYCERIDES (TG)

The TRIGL test is a colorimetric enzymatic method.

The present method is based on the work of Wahlefeld and uses a lipoprotein lipase obtained from microorganisms to completely and rapidly hydrolyse triglycerides to glycerol, with subsequent oxidation to dihydroxyacetone phosphate and hydrogen peroxide. The hydrogen peroxide formed reacts under the catalytic action of peroxidase with 4-aminophenazone and 4-chlorophenol to form a red dye in a Trinder end-point reaction. The color intensity of the red dye formed is directly proportional to the triglyceride concentration and can be measured photometrically.

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Calibration

Calibration interval: Perform Two-Point Calibration:

- with each lot of reagents
- if necessary according to quality control procedures

Quality Control

Carry out quality control with PreciControl ClinChem Multi.

Adapt control ranges and limits to individual laboratory requirements. Results must be within defined limits.

Each laboratory should establish corrective measures to follow in case the values are outside the defined limits.

Limits and intervals

- Measurement range: 0.1-10 mmol/L (8.85-885 mg/dL).
- Lower limits of measurement:
Lower limit of detection: 0.1 mmol/L (8.85 mg/dL).

The lower limit of detection is the lowest measurable analyte concentration that can be distinguished from zero. It is calculated as the value 3 standard deviations above the lowest standard (standard 1 + 3 SD, repeatability, n = 21).

Precision

Precision was determined using human samples and controls according to an internal protocol with repeatability (n = 21) and intermediate precision (3 aliquots per series, 1 series per day, 21 days). The following results were obtained:

Table 27: Repeatability and intermediate precision values obtained for TRIGL test

Sample	Repeatability			Intermediate precision		
	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %	Median (mmol/L)	DE (mmol/L)	CV %
Human serum 1	1.67	0.02	1.1	1.18	0.02	1.9
Human serum 2	2.72	0.02	0.7	2.95	0.05	1.8
Precinorm U	1.41	0.01	0.9	1.39	0.03	2.0
Precipath U	2.40	0.02	0.8	2.95	0.04	1.6

Analysis limitations – interferences

Recovery within $\pm 10\%$ of baseline values with a triglycerides concentration of 2.3 mmol/L (203 mg/dL).

Icterus: No significant interference up to an index I of 10 for conjugated bilirubin and 35 for unconjugated bilirubin, which is equivalent to an approximate concentration of conjugated bilirubin of 171 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 10 mg / dL and an approximate concentration of unconjugated bilirubin 599 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 35 mg / dL.

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Hemolysis: No significant interference up to an index H of 700 (hemoglobin concentration: approximately 434 $\mu\text{mol} / \text{L}$ or 700 mg / dL).

Lipemia (Intralipid): the index L is correlated with the turbidity of the sample but not with the level of triglycerides. Extremely lipemic samples (with triglyceride values greater than 3000 mg / dL) can produce normal results.

Lim. Prozone: The > Kin prompt indicates extremely high triglyceride concentrations in the sample. False normal results are due to oxygen depletion during the analytical reaction.

If the serum sample contains endogenous unesterified glycerol, falsely elevated triglyceride values may be obtained.

At therapeutic concentrations, Dicynone (ethamsylate) can cause falsely low values.

Drugs: No interference has been recorded with panels of commonly used drugs at therapeutic concentrations. Exception: ascorbic acid and calcium dobesilate cause artificially low triglyceride results. The present test directly determines Intralipid as one more analyte, causing its existence high triglyceride results.

Paracetamol poisoning is usually treated with N-acetylcysteine. Both N-acetylcysteine, at plasma concentrations above 166 mg / L, and the paracetamol metabolite, N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), can cause falsely low values.

Venipuncture should be done before administering metamizole. If venipuncture is performed immediately after or during administration of metamizole, falsely low results may be obtained. Significant interference can be obtained with plasma metamizole concentrations greater than 0.05 mg / mL.

In unusual cases, false results may be obtained due to gammopathy, particularly of the IgM type (Waldenström macroglobulinemia).

4.6 Urinary 8OHdG concentrations (MU)

4.6.1 Method details

4.6.1.1 Chemicals

Standard 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG, 98 %) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck); 15N5-8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (>95 %) were obtained from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories; MS grade acetonitrile, isopropanol and formic acid (FA, 99%) were purchased from BIOSOLVE BV (Netherlands).

4.6.1.2 Urine sample treatment and extraction

The urine samples kept in $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were thawed at room temperature and vortexed. The 10 μL of internal standard 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG (15N5-8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine; 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in 0.1% v/v formic acid) was added to 0.5 mL of each urine samples (or to calibration solutions of 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine; 0, 0.05, 0.5, 5, 50 ng/mL in 0.1% v/v formic acid) using 2 mL plastic vials. Samples were well vortexed, then frozen at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight and lyophilized/freeze-dried for 24h. Dry urine and calibration samples were re-suspended in 0.5 mL of isopropanol and extracted in ultrasonic bath for 15 min. Insoluble particles were removed by centrifugation ($12,000 \times g$, $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 10 min), 350 μL of supernatant was transferred in glass vials and evaporated by stream of nitrogen to dryness (approx. 15 min), and re-dissolved in 250 μL of 0.1% v/v formic acid using ultrasonic bath and vortex. Residual particles were removed by microspin filters (0.2 μm ; cellulose acetate;

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10 000 x g, 3 min, 10 °C, Fisher Scientific). Filtrates in glass vials were stored in -80 °C until the analyses of 8-OHdG by LC-MS/MS.

4.6.1.3 Chromatography and mass spectrometry conditions

Analyses of 8-OHdG were performed with Waters Acquity LC chromatograph (Waters, Manchester, U.K.) consisting of a vacuum degasser, a binary pump, a thermostatted autosampler, and a column compartment. The column used was an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 (1.7 µm) (Waters) 100 x 2.1 mm equipped with a guard pre-column kept at 25°C. Detection was performed on a Xevo TQ-S quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters Manchester, U.K.) equipped with electrospray ionisation. Analytes after ESI ionisation were detected in positive ion mode using tandem mass spectrometry with multiple reaction monitoring (MRM). Data were processed by MassLynxTM software (Manchester, U.K.).

The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid in water (A) and acetonitrile acidified by 0.1% formic acid (B). The binary pump gradient was linear (5% B at 0-1 min, then increases from 5% B at 1 min to 80% B at 5 min and 80% B was kept for 2 min) followed by 4 min column equilibration to the initial conditions (5% B). The flow rate was 0.2 mL/min, and 10 µL of individual sample from the thermostatted autosampler (10°C) was injected for the analyses. The ionisation parameters were as follows: capillary voltage, 2.5kV; the source temperature and the desolvation temperature, 150 and 750 °C, respectively; the cone gas flow, 150 (L/h); the cone voltages, 30 V; the desolvation gas flow, 750 (L/h); and the collision gas flow, 0.15 mL/min. The following *m/z* transitions of 8-OHdG were monitored: *m/z* 284.1 > 168.1 (quantifier; collision energy 14V), *m/z* 284.1 > 140.1 (qualifier; collision energy 28V) and average ratio of quantifier (*m/z* 168.1) ions to qualifier (*m/z* 140.1) was 5.1±0.6 (N=30). The *m/z* transition for internal standard 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG were also monitored: *m/z* 289.1 > 173.1 (quantifier; collision energy 14V) and *m/z* 289.1 > 141.1 (qualifier; collision energy 28V). Concentration of 8-OHdG were corrected for the content of internal standard and expressed as microgram per litter of urine as well as microgram per gram of creatinine.

The example of LC-MS/MS chromatograms obtained in multiple reaction monitoring mode (MRM) for 8-OHdG and 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG in a standard solution and urinary sample are shown in **Figure 27. 1**.

Panel A

Panel B

Figure 27: Example LC-MS/MS chromatograms. Panel (A) - standard (0.5 ng/mL) and internal standard: 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG. Panel (B) – chromatogram for urine sample spiked with 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG

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4.6.2 Validation details

Validation of the methodology included characterisation of

- calibration linearity
- limits of detection and quantification
- precision
- analyte recovery

Linearity of the method was assessed by repeated analysis of the calibration solutions processed in the same way as the urine samples (four points). The calibration curve for 8-OHdG was linear for concentrations 0.05-0.5-5-50 ng/mL ($r^2=0.999$) and the coefficients of variance (CV in %) of the independent calibration solutions prepared in 3 different days did not exceed 24% for any concentration. Each of the calibration solutions and samples contained 10 ng/mL of 15N5-labeled 8-OHdG. **Figure 28** shows an example calibration curve along with the distribution of residues.

Compound name: 8OHdG
 Correlation coefficient: $r = 0.999834$, $r^2 = 0.999667$
 Calibration curve: $0.652143 * x + 0.00288935$
 Response type: Internal Std (Ref 3), Area * (IS Conc. / IS Area)
 Curve type: Linear, Origin: Exclude, Weighting: 1/x, Axis trans: None

Figure 28: Calibration curve for 8-OH-dG

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The precision of the method was evaluated by performing replicate determinations of 8-OHdG in three different urine extracts (no reference material is currently commercially available). The coefficients of variation were 3.9–5.2 and 6.8–9.6 % for intra-day (N=5) and inter-day (N=5) variability tests, respectively. Data are presented in **Table 27**.

Table 27: Assessment of intra- and inter-day variability in 8-OH-dG analyses in urine. Each analysis of the sample was repeated five times (5 repeated analyses within one day, and 5 repeated analyses independently in 5 different days)

	Urine sample No. 1	Urine sample No. 2	Urine sample No. 3
Within one day (intra-day) variability (mean±SD; N=5), ng/mL (in parenthesis - CV in %)	2.13±0.11 (5.16)	6.35±0.31 (4.87)	10.07±0.39 (3.85)
Inter-day variability (mean±SD; N=5), ng/mL (in parenthesis - CV in %)	2.23±0.22 (9.64)	6.28±0.43 (6.82)	9.80±0.88 (8.93)

The instrumental limit of detection (LOD) 0.025 ng/mL was determined as the concentration that yielded a signal to noise (S/N) ratio > 3 using diluted standard solutions and the limit of quantification (LOQ) as 0.05 ng/mL (S/N > 10).

The recoveries of the total extraction procedure of 8-OHdG were 101 ± 5%, 98 ± 7% and 100 ± 5% in five replicates of standard solutions 0.5, 5 and 50 ng/mL, respectively. Standard solutions (**Table 28**) were processed in the same way as the urine samples.

Table 28: Assessment of 8-OH-dG recovery from standard solution

Replicate	0.5 ng/mL	5 ng/mL	50 ng/mL
1	0.55	5.38	49.07
2	0.49	4.75	47.17
3	0.51	4.45	49.91
4	0.49	5.08	50.36
5	0.49	4.89	53.32
Mean ± SD (ng/mL)	0.51±0.03	4.91±0.35	49.77±2.24
Recovery (mean ± SD in %)	101.2±5.1	98.2±7.0	99.9±4.5

Validation of the recovery was also performed by the extraction of spiked urine sample with known concentration of 8-OHdG (2.13±0.11 ng/mL, N=5) after external additions of two 8-OHdG concentrations (5 and 50 ng/mL), **Table 29**. The recovery based on two replicated analyses of both spiked concentrations ranged between 95 to 106%.

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Table 29: Assessment of 8-OH-dG recovery from urine sample (nature content of 8-OHdG was subtracted)

Replicate	5 ng/mL	50 ng/mL
1	5.3	47.6
2	4.9	49.8
Recovery - range (%)	98-106	95-98
Recovery – mean (CV in %)	102.0 (5.8)	96.6 (2.0)

4.7 Conclusions and Next Steps

Overall, the technical validation of all novel biomarkers has been completed. Some of them have been implemented in the INMA-Granada birth cohort as a pilot study for feasibility and validity before its implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Some positive results have been observed regarding the physiological validity of these measurements (e.g. BDNF methylation and serum total BDNF levels are correlated, and are linked to behavioural data; but not for urinary BDNF levels in the assessed study population). Thus, these biomarkers are ready to be implemented in human samples collected from the HBM4EU aligned studies, as a second and final step (**Table 30**).

Table 30: State of development of each effect biomarker type

Effect biomarker	Partner	Assay	Technically validated?	Implemented in INMA-Granada pilot?	Next Step
Serum BDNF protein levels	UGR	ELISA	Yes	Yes	Ready to implement in aligned studies
Urinary BDNF protein levels	UGR	ELISA	Yes	Yes	Study physiological validity in INMA-Granada before implementation **
Blood DNA methylation	INSERM	Bisulfite-Pyrosequencing	Yes	Yes for BDNF Being implemented for Kisspeptin	Ready to implement in aligned studies
Serum Kisspeptin levels	UGR	ELISA	Yes	Yes	Study physiological validity in INMA-Granada before implementation ***
Histone modification of nuclear receptors	INSERM	Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP)	Yes	Yes	Ready to implement in aligned studies
Urinary 8OHdG levels	MU	HPLC-MS/MS	Yes	Not needed*	Ready to implement in aligned studies
Serum hormonal and metabolic classic parameters	UGR	Immunosorbent assays	Yes	Yes	Ready to implement in aligned studies

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* In the case of 8OHdG, it is known that urine is the best matrix to assess this biomarker, and that good variability exists in different populations (Steffensen et al., 2020).

** Before implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies, we will check the range and variability of urinary BDNF measurements, if urinary BDNF concentrations correlate with serum and blood BDNF biomarkers in the same children, as well as with neurodevelopmental data to explore the physiological validity of this marker.

*** Before implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies, we will check the range and variability of kisspeptin measurements, and its relationship with kisspeptin DNA methylation and other steroid hormones (LH, FSH, TT, E2, SHBG, etc.), to provide data on the physiological validity of this marker.

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5 References

- Aksu, S., Unlu, G., Kardesler, A.C., Cakaloz, B., Aybek, H., 2018. Altered levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor, proBDNF and tissue plasminogen activator in children with posttraumatic stress disorder. *Psychiatry Res.* 268, 478–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2018.07.013>
- Alkis, O., Zumrutbas, A.E., Toktas, C., Aybek, H., Aybek, Z., 2017. The use of biomarkers in the diagnosis and treatment of overactive bladder: Can we predict the patients who will be resistant to treatment? *Neurourol. Urodyn.* 36, 390–393. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nau.22939>
- Alomari, M.A., Al-sheyab, N.A., Khabour, O.F., Alzoubi, K.H., 2018. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in adolescents smoking waterpipe: The Irbid TRY. *Int. J. Dev. Neurosci.* 67, 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdevneu.2018.03.007>
- Antunes-Lopes, T., Coelho, A., Pinto, R., Barros, S.C., Cruz, C.D., Cruz, F., Silva, C.M., 2017. Urinary Neurotrophin Levels Increase in Women With Stress Urinary Incontinence After a Midurethral Sling Procedure. *Urology* 99, 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urology.2016.08.048>
- Antunes-Lopes, T., Pinto, R., Barros, S.C., Botelho, F., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C.D., Cruz, F., 2013. Urinary Neurotrophic Factors in Healthy Individuals and Patients with Overactive Bladder. *J. Urol.* 189, 359–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2012.08.187>
- Autry, A.E., Monteggia, L.M., 2012. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and neuropsychiatric disorders. *Pharmacol. Rev.* 64, 238–58. <https://doi.org/10.1124/pr.111.005108>
- Bathina, S., Das, U.N., 2015. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and its clinical implications. *Arch. Med. Sci.* 6, 1164–1178. <https://doi.org/10.5114/aoms.2015.56342>
- Bauer, M., Fink, B., Thürmann, L., Eszlinger, M., Herberth, G., Lehmann, I., 2016. Tobacco smoking differently influences cell types of the innate and adaptive immune system—indications from CpG site methylation. *Clin. Epigenetics* 8, 83. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13148-016-0249-7>
- Castiello, F., Olmedo, P., Gil, F., Molina, M., Mundo, A., Romero, R.R., Ruíz, C., Gómez-Vida, J., Vela-Soria, F., Freire, C., 2020. Association of urinary metal concentrations with blood pressure and serum hormones in Spanish male adolescents. *Environ. Res.* 182, 108958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108958>
- Chen, S.F., Jiang, Y.H., Kuo, H.C., 2017. Urinary biomarkers in patients with detrusor underactivity with and without bladder function recovery. *Int. Urol. Nephrol.* 49, 1763–1770. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11255-017-1666-z>
- Cho, S.Y., So, W.Y., Roh, H.T., 2017. The effects of taekwondo training on peripheral Neuroplasticity-Related growth factors, cerebral blood flow velocity, and cognitive functions in healthy children: A randomized controlled trial. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14050454>
- Collins, L.R., Koven, N.S., 2014. Urinary BDNF-to-creatinine ratio is associated with aerobic fitness. *Neurosci. Lett.* 559, 169–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2013.12.004>
- Ece, A., Coşkun, S., Şahin, C., Tan, Karabel, D., Çim, A., 2019. BDNF and NGF gene polymorphisms and urine BDNF–NGF levels in children with primary monosymptomatic nocturnal enuresis. *J. Pediatr. Urol.* 15, 255.e1-255.e7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpuro.2019.03.010>
- F., R., G., C., G., R., M., L., B., D., C., C., A., O., 2018. Adipose Tissue-Derived Biomarkers of Intestinal Barrier Functions for the Characterization of Diarrhoea-Predominant IBS. *Dis. Markers* 2018, 1827937. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/1827937> LK -

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<http://resolver.ebscohost.com/openurl?sid=EMBASE&issn=18758630&id=doi:10.1155%2F2018%2F1827937&atitle=Adipose+Tissue->

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Fonseca-Portilla, R., Krell-Roesch, J., Shaibi, G.Q., Caselli, R.J., Mandarino, L.J., Zhang, N., Hentz, J.G., Coletta, D.K., De Filippis, E.A., Dawit, S., Geda, Y.E., 2019. Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor and Its Associations with Metabolism and Physical Activity in a Latino Sample. *Metab. Syndr. Relat. Disord.* 17, 75–80. <https://doi.org/10.1089/met.2018.0028>

Gorkem, U., Togrul, C., Arslan, E., Sargin Oruc, A., Buyukkayaci Duman, N., 2018. Is there a role for kisspeptin in pathogenesis of polycystic ovary syndrome? *Gynecol. Endocrinol.* 34, 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09513590.2017.1379499>

Huang, T., Gejl, A.K., Tarp, J., Andersen, L.B., Peijs, L., Bugge, A., 2017. Cross-sectional associations of objectively measured physical activity with brain-derived neurotrophic factor in adolescents. *Physiol. Behav.* 171, 87–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2016.12.026>

J.M., K., 2016. Relationships between brain-derived neurotrophic factor promoter methylation, childhood adversities, and suicidal behavior in depressive patients. *J. Am. Acad. Child Adolesc. Psychiatry* 55, S249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2016.09.456> LK -

<http://resolver.ebscohost.com/openurl?sid=EMBASE&issn=15275418&id=doi:10.1016%2Fj.jaac.2016.09.456&atitle=Relationships+between+brain->

[derived+neurotrophic+factor+promoter+methylation%2C+childhood+adversities%2C+and+suicidal+behavior+in+depressive+patients&stitle=J.+Am.+Acad.+Child+Adolesc.+Psychiatry&title=Journal+of+the+American+Academy+of+Child+and+Adolescent+Psychiatry&volume=55&issue=10&spage=S249&epage=&aulast=Kim&aufirst=Jae+Min&aunit=J.M.&aufull=Kim+J.M.&](http://resolver.ebscohost.com/openurl?sid=EMBASE&issn=15275418&id=doi:10.1016%2Fj.jaac.2016.09.456&atitle=Relationships+between+brain-derived+neurotrophic+factor+promoter+methylation%2C+childhood+adversities%2C+and+suicidal+behavior+in+depressive+patients&stitle=J.+Am.+Acad.+Child+Adolesc.+Psychiatry&title=Journal+of+the+American+Academy+of+Child+and+Adolescent+Psychiatry&volume=55&issue=10&spage=S249&epage=&aulast=Kim&aufirst=Jae+Min&aunit=J.M.&aufull=Kim+J.M.&)

Jeon, Y.K., Ha, C.H., 2017. The effect of exercise intensity on brain derived neurotrophic factor and memory in adolescents. *Environ. Health Prev. Med.* 22, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-017-0643-6>

Jiang, Y.-H., Liu, H.-T., Kuo, H.-C., 2014. Decrease of Urinary Nerve Growth Factor but Not Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor in Patients with Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome Treated with Hyaluronic Acid. *PLoS One* 9, e91609. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091609>

K., Ö., N., D., A., B., S., M., 2016. Can Urinary Nerve Growth Factor and Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor be used in the Diagnosis and Follow-Up of Voiding Dysfunction in Children? *Urol. J.* 13, 2690–2696.

Koven, N.S., Collins, L.R., 2014. Urinary brain-derived neurotrophic factor as a biomarker of executive functioning. *Neuropsychobiology* 69, 227–34. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000362242>

Kowiański, P., Lietzau, G., Czuba, E., Waśkow, M., Steliga, A., Moryś, J., 2018. BDNF: A Key Factor with Multipotent Impact on Brain Signaling and Synaptic Plasticity. *Cell. Mol. Neurobiol.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10571-017-0510-4>

Kundakovic, M., Gudsnuk, K., Herbstman, J.B., Tang, D., Perera, F.P., Champagne, F.A., 2015. DNA methylation of BDNF as a biomarker of early-life adversity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112, 6807–6813. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1408355111>

D14.7 - QA/QC measures for effect biomarkers	Security: Public
WP14 - Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: M.F. Fernández, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, V. Mustieles and N. Olea	Page: 69

Li, W., He, Q.Z., Wu, C.Q., Pan, X.Y., Wang, J., Tan, Y., Shan, X.Y., Zeng, H.C., 2015. PFOS Disturbs BDNF-ERK-CREB Signalling in Association with Increased MicroRNA-22 in SH-SY5Y Cells. *Biomed Res. Int.* 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/302653>

Lu, B., Nagappan, G., Lu, Y., 2014. BDNF and Synaptic Plasticity, Cognitive Function, and Dysfunction, in: *Handbook of Experimental Pharmacology*. pp. 223–250. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-45106-5_9

Mora, E., Portella, M.J., Piñol-Ripoll, G., López, R., Cuadras, D., Forcada, I., Teres, M., Vieta, E., Mur, M., 2019. High BDNF serum levels are associated to good cognitive functioning in bipolar disorder. *Eur. Psychiatry* 60, 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2019.02.006>

Morizawa, Y., Aoki, K., Iemura, Y., Hori, S., Gotoh, D., Fukui, S., Nakai, Y., Miyake, M., Torimoto, K., Tanaka, N., Fujimoto, K., 2019. Urinary nerve growth factor can predict therapeutic efficacy in children with monosymptomatic nocturnal enuresis. *Neurourol. Urodyn.* 38, 2311–2317. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nau.24142>

Naegelin, Y., Dingsdale, H., Säuberli, K., Schädelin, S., Kappos, L., Barde, Y.A., 2018. Measuring and validating the levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor in human serum. *eNeuro* 5, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0419-17.2018>

Oddone, F., Roberti, G., Micera, A., Busanello, A., Bonini, S., Quaranta, L., Agnifili, L., Manni, G., 2017. Exploring Serum Levels of Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor and Nerve Growth Factor Across Glaucoma Stages. *PLoS One* 12, e0168565. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0168565>

Orlando, G., Leone, S., Ferrante, C., Chiavaroli, A., Mollica, A., Stefanucci, A., Macedonio, G., Dimmito, M.P., Leporini, L., Menghini, L., Brunetti, L., Recinella, L., 2018. Effects of kisspeptin-10 on hypothalamic neuropeptides and neurotransmitters involved in appetite control. *Molecules* 23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23123071>

Ormstad, H., Bryn, V., Verkerk, R., Skjeldal, O.H., Halvorsen, B., Saugstad, O.D., Isaksen, J., Maes, M., 2018. Serum tryptophan, tryptophan catabolites and brain-derived neurotrophic factor in subgroups of youngsters with autism spectrum disorders. *CNS Neurol. Disord. - Drug Targets* 17, 626–639. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1871527317666180720163221>

Pedersen, N.H., Tarp, J., Andersen, L.B., Gejl, A.K., Huang, T., Peijs, L., Bugge, A., 2017. The association between serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor and a cluster of cardiovascular risk factors in adolescents: The CHAMPS-study DK. *PLoS One* 12, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186384>

Pennycuff, J.F., Schutte, S.C., Hudson, C.O., Karp, D.R., Malykhina, A.P., Northington, G.M., 2017. Urinary neurotrophic peptides in postmenopausal women with and without overactive bladder. *Neurourol. Urodyn.* 36, 740–744. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nau.23011>

Perera, F., Phillips, D.H., Wang, Y., Roen, E., Herbstman, J., Rauh, V., Wang, S., Tang, D., 2015. Prenatal exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons/aromatics, BDNF and child development. *Environ. Res.* 142, 602–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.08.011>

Peyronnet, B., Richard, C., Bendavid, C., Naudet, F., Hascoet, J., Brochard, C., Senal, N., Jezequel, M., Alimi, Q., Khene, Z., Corlu, A., Clément, B., Siproudhis, L., Bouguen, G., Kerdraon, J., Manunta, A., Gamé, X., 2019. Urinary TIMP-2 and MMP-2 are significantly associated with poor bladder compliance in adult patients with spina bifida. *Neurourol. Urodyn.* 38, 2151–2158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nau.24163>

D14.7 - QA/QC measures for effect biomarkers	Security: Public
WP14 - Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: M.F. Fernández, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, V. Mustieles and N. Olea	Page: 70

Piccinni, A., Marazziti, D., Del Debbio, A., Bianchi, C., Roncaglia, I., Mannari, C., Origlia, N., Catena Dell'Osso, M., Massimetti, G., Domenici, L., Dell'Osso, L., 2008. Diurnal variation of plasma brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) in humans: An analysis of sex differences. *Chronobiol. Int.* 25, 819–826. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07420520802387773>

Pinto, R., Lopes, T., Frias, B., Silva, A., Silva, J.A., Silva, C.M., Cruz, C., Cruz, F., Dinis, P., 2010. Trigonal injection of botulinum toxin A in patients with refractory bladder pain syndrome/interstitial cystitis. *Eur. Urol.* 58, 360–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2010.02.031>

Popa, S.M., Clifton, D.K., Steiner, R.A., 2008. The role of kisspeptins and GPR54 in the neuroendocrine regulation of reproduction. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 70, 213–238. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.physiol.70.113006.100540>

Rada, M.P., Ciortea, R., Măluțan, A.M., Doumouchtsis, S.K., Bucuri, C.E., Clim, A., Roman, A., Mișu, D., 2020. The profile of urinary biomarkers in overactive bladder. *Neurourol. Urodyn.* 39, 2305–2313. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nau.24487>

Wang, L., Wang, Li, J., Long, Yu, Y., Xiao, R., Hai, Huang, H., Wei, Kuang, R., Rui, Hai, B., 2017. Association of increased urine brain derived neurotrophic factor with lower urinary tract symptoms in men with benign prostatic hyperplasia. *J. Huazhong Univ. Sci. Technol. - Med. Sci.* 37, 531–535. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11596-017-1768-y>

Wang, L.W., Han, X.M., Chen, C.H., Ma, Y., Hai, B., 2014. Urinary brain-derived neurotrophic factor: A potential biomarker for objective diagnosis of overactive bladder. *Int. Urol. Nephrol.* 46, 341–347. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11255-013-0540-x>

Yurteri, N., Şahin, İ.E., Tufan, A.E., 2019. Altered serum levels of vascular endothelial growth factor and glial-derived neurotrophic factor but not fibroblast growth factor-2 in treatment-naïve children with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Nord. J. Psychiatry* 73, 302–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08039488.2019.1625437>

Zhao, G., Zhang, C., Chen, J., Su, Y., Zhou, R., Wang, F., Xia, W., Huang, J., Wang, Z., Hu, Y., Cao, L., Guo, X., Yuan, C., Wang, Y., Yi, Z., Lu, W., Wu, Y., Wu, Z., Hong, W., Peng, D., Fang, Y., 2017. Ratio of mBDNF to proBDNF for Differential Diagnosis of Major Depressive Disorder and Bipolar Depression. *Mol. Neurobiol.* 54, 5573–5582. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-016-0098-6>

Zhu, H.J., Li, S.J., Pan, H., Li, N., Zhang, D.X., Wang, L.J., Yang, H.B., Wu, Q., Gong, F.Y., 2016. The Changes of Serum Leptin and Kisspeptin Levels in Chinese Children and Adolescents in Different Pubertal Stages. *Int. J. Endocrinol.* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/6790794>

Zuccato, C., Cattaneo, E., 2009. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in neurodegenerative diseases. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* 5, 311–22. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneurol.2009.54>